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Master Thesis

**Optimized access to ATLAS analyses
within THE ROOT Framework**

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Umesh Dharmaji Worlikar, declare that this thesis titled, “Optimized access to ATLAS analyses within THE ROOT Framework” and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This dissertation towards the completion of my master thesis is the outcome of my own independent work.
- This thesis has not been published or submitted previously for a degree or any other qualification at this university or any other institution.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, I have taken utmost care to ensure that the work is clearly attributed to the source.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is clearly specified. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all the main sources of help.

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The prototype software developed during this thesis task is available at the following open source repository: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/uworlika/xaod-ds>

Abstract

Umesh Dharmaji Worlikar

*Optimized access to ATLAS analyses
within THE ROOT Framework*

This thesis seeks a general solution to optimize ATLAS data analyses using a proposed method of data access within the ROOT framework. The current work prototypes a proof-of-concept for a package – “xAOD Data Source”: A thin layer between the ROOT and ATLAS analysis framework. Conceptually, this method abstracts away the complexities of parallelism from the physics analysis code using new interfaces of the ROOT framework. This abstraction lets data analysts focus on physics, while the framework uses implicit parallelism for performance improvement. This thesis documents the design, implementation, validation, and optimization of the above-referred prototype. Furthermore, it demonstrates the performance benefits using the results of preliminary testing and profiling. The project thus opens up potential opportunities for the addition of some scalable and user-friendly features into current ATLAS analysis framework.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 High Energy Physics

Data analysis is a crucial step in the process of resolving open scientific questions. Such a process usually begins with the collection of data from suitably designed experiments, followed by several data preparation steps, and then the comparison of measurements with predictions from mathematical models and theories. One of the prominent application areas of such a process is High Energy Physics (HEP) which seeks a better understanding of fundamental constituents of matter and the nature of interactions between them. At CERN[8], the European Organization for Nuclear Research, physicists and engineers from several collaborations around the world, probe the fundamental structure of the universe to understand phenomena such as the origin of matter, its fundamental building blocks and the interaction forces among them, collectively referred to as “The Standard Model”[58] – the theory supported by a great deal of experimental evidence.

1.2 The Large Hadron Collider (LHC)

CERN hosts several experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC)[34], the world’s largest and most powerful particle accelerator. It consists of a 27-kilometer ring of superconducting magnets, with multiple accelerating structures to boost the energy of particles successively. The common purpose of these experiments is to create conditions resembling “The Big Bang” [57] event. Within an accelerator, the particles are accelerated to a speed close to that of light, forming a beam carrying several bunches of particles. Two such particle beams traveling in the opposite direction are made to intersect causing head-on collisions of particles. These collisions and their outcomes are observed using detector equipment, referred to as experiments. LHC is equipped with seven such experiments[29]. Each one is characterized by its detector equipment and run by collaborations of scientists from institutes all over the world. The biggest two of these, ATLAS and CMS, use general purpose detectors designed to investigate the largest range of physics possible. The ALICE experiment studies lead-ion collisions to recreate the conditions just after the Big Bang. The LHCb experiment studies the observed asymmetry between matter and antimatter. The TOTEM experiment focuses on specific phenomena such as the measurement of the effective size of the proton. The LHCf experiment simulates cosmic rays in laboratory conditions. The MoEDAL experiment searches for hypothetical particles such as magnetic monopoles.

FIGURE 1.1: LHC/HL-LHC Plan, Source: HEP Software Foundation: Roadmap for the 2020s [16]

1.3 Data Analysis in HEP

The particle collisions within a detector often generate new particles, which decay into even more particles. A complex series of detectors and calorimeters precisely measure these outcomes referred to as “Collision Events”. The particles travel along the beams in the form of bunches. Up to about 40 million [29] such bunches cross per second inside the detector. A trigger system filters this data to select a smaller subset of collision events. This data is then stored and prepared for further analysis. A typical analysis model follows successive stages of data reduction, keeping smaller subsets of data relevant to the specific area of exploration. These steps are executed using a wide range of HEP computing tools. Most of these tools heavily use an ecosystem of software based on ROOT [2], a general purpose object-oriented framework of utility software libraries for statistical analysis and data visualization.

The HEP Software Foundation [16] has set up a long-term plan for the particle physics program which involves conducting experiments at higher energies and with greater complexities. Figure 1.1 shows the estimated timeline with two future phases identified as LHC: Run 3 and the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) [25]. These milestones involve a significant investment to upgrade the existing experiments, both in terms of detector equipment and software frameworks. Higher energies and greater complexities of experiments are anticipated to result into a substantial increment in the size and the complexity of the data. Existing data analysis frameworks are therefore preparing to address these requirements, aiming at higher computing efficiencies and scalable solutions.

1.4 Motivation

Given the anticipated growth of data size and complexity, the efficiency of analysis framework is a prime requirement of experiments and physics groups. This work seeks a scalable solution for efficiency improvement in the ATLAS analysis framework. In this context, the framework efficiency is interpreted in two aspects as outlined below:

- **Analysis Execution Time:** The recent trend [45] of hardware evolution indicates that more and more computing power is coming from the increased number of CPU cores, rather than increased clock speed [51]. It follows that serial programs cannot gain any further performance improvements by merely relying on clock speeds of processors. Therefore, parallel computing has rather become a prerequisite for HEP applications. Ongoing efforts in Research and Development (R&D) of parallel computing are preparing the HEP software to utilize the multi-core hardware effectively. These approaches [10] include the investigation of opportunities for possible parallelism at the event-level, algorithm level and also within algorithms. This work attempts to investigate the possible use of event-level parallelism for ATLAS analyses.
- **Analysis Development Time:** Concerning the usability of the analysis framework, the prominent components of the analysis development time include the efforts involved in the programming, setup, and configuration of the analysis code. To this end, a functional and declarative programming model allows analysts to define the analysis as a set of transforms applied on the data. Instead of explicitly coding the control of a program, the analyst can focus on physics of the problem. The framework then handles computing aspects to exploit the available hardware for efficient execution. This abstraction hides the computing complexity of implementations from the analyst, thereby improving developer productivity. Consequently, this separation also provides more freedom to the framework for the optimization to adapt diverse forms of computing resources. This work investigates the possible use of such an abstraction for ATLAS analyses.

In the following, two major recent upgrades [10] in the ROOT framework are outlined. These upgrades motivated the investigation of using new features of ROOT for the ATLAS analysis framework. Both these upgrades were aimed at the framework efficiency and the developer productivity.

The first upgrade was the change of C++ interpreter from `CINT` [9] to `Cling` [11], which supports compilation of the code during the program execution, referred to as Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation. This feature allows ROOT's type system to evolve their reflection and I/O capabilities with the latest C++ standard. Consequent feature upgrades thus allowed ROOT to support declarative syntax to simplify the analysis configuration.

The second upgrade was the introduction of the "Implicit MT" [43] feature, which hides the complexity of parallelization behind abstract interfaces. This abstraction allows ROOT to separate the configuration of even-loop execution from the definition of analysis steps. The ROOT configures and executes the event-loop using all available parallelism implicitly. As a consequence, the analysis code takes the form of simple declarative statements and lets the analyst focus on the physics of the problem rather than computing details.

Built on top of these features, the recent ROOT releases are aimed at the performance improvement in several modules. Two of such notable examples are I/O performance improvements and the introduction of "RDataFrame" [38], a collection of user interfaces and classes. The I/O performance improvements [21] are pursued by parallel (de)serialization/(de)compression techniques and writing the data

to files using parallel merging techniques. The analysis performance improvements are pursued by implicit parallel execution of the event-loop behind the `RDataFrame` interface.

This work aims to utilize the above-referred features for the ATLAS analyses. In particular, the implicit parallelism for analysis performance and declarative interfaces for developer productivity. The overall objective is to develop a prototype – “xAOD Data Source” (`DataSource`) as a proof-of-concept and evaluate its performance using a set of analysis use cases. This effort also provides an opportunity to identify possible challenges which may evolve during the integration of this prototype with the existing tools/frameworks, and attempt to propose future improvements.

1.5 Thesis outline

The rest of this thesis documents the findings from the study of existing tools and frameworks, followed by a detailed discussion of this prototyping activity and concludes with the findings during the validation phase.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the ATLAS Event Data Model and various methods available for accessing analysis data.

Chapter 3 describes fundamental building blocks of ROOT’s I/O system and the new `RDataFrame` interface. It lists various analysis features offered by `RDataFrame`, followed by the explanation of its workflow.

Chapter 4 begins with an overview of design principles and patterns as a motivation behind the design objectives of this prototype. It then describes the design of major components of xAOD Data Source, followed by a detailed discussion of the implementation. It further explains the process followed for the verification and validation of this work. This includes error/exception handling strategy, exception guarantees, integration testing and a brief description of the unit testing setup.

Chapter 5 reports performance test observations and initial findings from profiling exercises. It further describes the optimization attempts made for performance tuning, followed by profiling observations and concludes with remarks on the known limitations.

Chapter 6 summarizes overall findings during this prototyping phase and concludes with current observations, and future directions.

Chapter 2

ATLAS: Event Data Model

This chapter provides an overview of the ATLAS experiment and its analysis software framework. This work relies on some of the foundation features of this framework for data access from files. The chapter begins with a brief overview of the ATLAS detector and the offline computing model, followed by a brief overview of data preparation workflow. It then describes the Event Data Model used by the ATLAS analyses and concludes with various data access methods provided by the framework. These access methods are considered as preliminary use cases steering the design of this prototype.

2.1 The ATLAS Experiment

ATLAS is one of the four major experiments at LHC, run by an international collaboration [14] of 182 institutions around the world, representing 38 countries [55]. It is a general-purpose particle physics experiment, designed to discover a wide range of physics. The detector itself is 44m long, 25m in diameter, and located 100m below ground inside the LHC cavern. The LHC accelerates two proton beams in the opposite direction, at an energy up to 7 TeV. These beams travel at a speed close to that of light and collide at the center of the ATLAS detector. These collisions result into newly formed particles, which spread out in all directions and decay into even more particles.

The detector subsystem layers are placed concentrically surrounding the collision point. They record various physical properties of particles, allowing them to be individually identified and measured. Figure 2.1 shows an overview of the ATLAS detector with its physical dimensions [14] and its subsystems. The detector consists of four major components. At the core, there is a set of **inner detectors**, which track the direction, momentum, and charge of electrically-charged particles produced by the collision. These detectors are surrounded by **calorimeters**, which measure the energy deposited by particles as they pass through calorimeters. Finally, the outermost layers consist of the **muon system**, which identifies muon particles and measures their momenta. In addition, a hybrid system of **superconducting magnets** facilitates bending the particle paths as they pass through the layers of detector systems to allow momentum determination.

ATLAS is designed to observe up to 40 million [29] proton-proton bunch-crossings per second. These collisions would potentially result in a data collection rate of more than 60 million MB/s. [56] However, due to practical constraints, the data can be written with a limiting frequency of 1KHz. Also, only a few of those original events are anticipated to be interesting for physics analysis. This huge amount of events are therefore filtered using a **trigger system**. This is accomplished in three successive

FIGURE 2.1: Cut-away view of the ATLAS detector, The ATLAS Collaboration [14]

layers of triggers, which finally reduce the data collection frequency to 200Hz. This data is then passed on to the data storage system and computing framework for further processing.

2.2 ATLAS Offline Computing Model

The data collected from a detector is in a binary format representing electrical signals. In order to represent it as physics objects, it is passed through a sequence of data preparation stages. The type and contents of the data vary broadly based on analysis domains and specific requirements of physics groups. For effective collaboration, it needs to be shared and accessed by physicists from around the world. In addition, the utilization of available computing resources such as storage space and network bandwidth influence data replication/distribution strategies. To address these challenges, CERN uses a distributed computing model based on the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) [69]. This facilitates the sharing of decentralized computing resources and enables efficient data access for all members of the collaboration. The rest of this section follows the ATLAS Technical Design Report [13] for LHC: Run 1, and the subsequent update [15] for LHC: Run 2. The ATLAS Offline Computing Model and various data preparation stages are briefly described below.

The type and configurations of computing resources are chosen to suit the different roles and requirements of physics groups. This variance implies a degree of hierarchy with distinct roles and applicable usage scenarios at each level. CERN accomplishes this using a Tier based classification of off-site facilities. The primary event processing occurs at CERN in Tier-0 facility. The RAW data is archived at CERN and copied along with the primary processed data to the Tier-1 facilities around the world. These facilities provide reprocessing and access to various processed data by physics analysis groups. The derived datasets produced by physics groups are

FIGURE 2.2: ATLAS: Data Preparation Stages. Based on ATLAS Software Tutorial [7]

copied to the Tier-2 facilities for further analysis. The Tier-2 facilities also provide the simulation capacity for the experiment with the simulated data housed at Tier-1 facilities. In addition, physicists can access the Grid through Tier-3 computing resources, which can consist of local clusters in universities. The data is also derived at several levels, such that it contains sufficient information relevant to the range of analysis tasks specific to physics analysis groups.

2.3 ATLAS Data Formats

Figure 2.2 shows an overview of ATLAS data preparation stages and corresponding data types. At the Tier-0 computing farm, the output of High-Level Trigger (HLT) is collected as a binary format of raw (RAW) data, which represents electrical signals. In order to prepare this data for physics analysis, these signals are reconstructed into object-oriented form to represent physical objects. These objects describe a wide range of particles (e.g., electrons, muons) and information about their behavior within the detector such as paths followed by them after collisions. The resulting data format of this reconstruction is Analysis Object Data (AOD). Based on the specific requirements of physics groups, this data is further reduced into subsets called the Derived AOD (DAOD). On the other hand, event simulation data is generated by various Monte-Carlo based event generators [4]. This step simulates proton collisions and subsequent interactions and decays of subatomic particles. The resulting data (EVNT) is then used to simulate the interactions of these particles with detector equipment. This step simulates the energy deposited by various particles, so-called hits (HITS) with the sensor elements of the detector. This information is in turn used to compute the detector response, through the digitization process, so that the output (RDO) “looks” like the raw format from the real detector. The digitization allows the reconstruction and further analysis steps to be identical for both real

and simulated data, although the simulated data also contains originally generated events referred as the “Monte-Carlo Truth”. From the data analysis perspective, the AOD format, therefore, is of particular interest.

The rest of this chapter takes a closer look at ATLAS (x)AOD format. In this context, the term AOD: Analysis Object Data, has the same meaning for both AOD and xAOD files. However, xAOD refers to the *data format* specifically designed for the timeline of LHC: Run 2 and the future. All the data preparation steps described above can be processed with – Athena, the ATLAS Offline Software Framework [5]. This framework provides an ecosystem of frequently used tools, services, and algorithms for reconstruction and analysis workflow referred above. However, the analysis step also can be processed using the stand-alone installation of the ROOT framework. This is possible due to the standardized xAOD format, irrespective of whether the data is simulated or originated from the detector. This standardization allows physicists to perform the data analysis without having a full installation of ATLAS software. The next section describes some benefits of this approach. This thesis is scoped to support this stand-alone ROOT based analysis workflow. i.e. for an isolated work environment with the installation of ROOT and the necessary libraries to access xAOD data format.

2.4 Event Data Model

This section provides an overview and motivation of the ATLAS Event Data Model (EDM). Following Krasznahorkay [28] and Buckley [6], some key features of the ATLAS xAOD data format and its implementation aspects for LHC: Run 2 are discussed.

The ATLAS EDM is an ecosystem of interfaces and concrete classes representing physics objects and relationships among them. The EDM framework facilitates modeling of collision events described by physical objects such as particles, in an object-oriented representation. It provides interfaces to manipulate collections of these objects, and analyze event information as required by common reconstruction and data analysis workflows. As a framework, the EDM defines basic building blocks of physics objects for their efficient access, in-memory representation, and storage to disk. Such a framework offers multiple advantages:

- It improves commonality and coherence across physics groups throughout all detector subsystems, reconstruction, and data analysis. In general, any given physics object has the same interface and behavior irrespective of its usage domain or the context of use case.
- It improves the use of standard software, as tools and services using framework defined interfaces can safely rely on code contracts, i.e. the preconditions, postconditions, and invariants specified for each operation. This specification minimizes the probability of unexpected results while sharing tools and algorithms across physics groups to support common use cases.
- It facilitates analysis and reconstruction developers to easily create and extend new objects using object-oriented [66] design concepts such as Inheritance, Polymorphism, and Encapsulation.

The AOD data format referred to in the previous section was implemented with these objectives and was successfully used during LHC: Run 1. However, the experience gained and observations made during Run 1, steered the evolution of new requirements [15] for Run 2 timeline. Following Buckley [6], a major limitation of Run 1 EDM was the complexity of I/O operations. The structure of event data was sufficiently complicated that it could not be directly written in ROOT format. This constraint needed a transformation of data from its transient representation to a persistent representation before writing it to the ROOT format. In addition to this overhead, it also introduced a strong dependency of ATLAS EDM on data files, making a full ATLAS release necessary for each access of data.

Consequently, most physics groups often preferred to convert the EDM data samples into smaller, ROOT-friendly formats. This approach had two adverse effects. First, it led to excessive duplication of data. Secondly, it complicated the maintenance of analysis tools of both categories. i.e. for full EDM usage and ROOT-friendly formats. Therefore, for Run 2, ATLAS redesigned a significant part of EDM used for analysis. This process was motivated with multiple design considerations as outlined below:

- Several types in Run 1 EDM supported the addition of new variables – “decorations”, to existing elements of containers. For example, an algorithm may iterate over all Jet objects and tag some of them with a variable such as `isSignal=true` if they pass an expensive selection criterion. Such decorations allow the algorithms to (re)use the dataset without (re)executing the selection criterion. However, depending on the application, this information may not need to be stored in the files. Thus the information intended to be strictly transient, should not participate in the I/O operations. Allowing decorations was originally intended to separate pieces of the data structure for efficient I/O, but the implementations were type-specific. As a consequence, there were several versions of decoration code, essentially doing the same thing in different ways. The challenge was to unify this functionality across all types.
- The data containers were stored as “arrays of structures” with each element as a separate C++ object. Even for a simple access pattern, (e.g., sequential traversal) such a container can cause poor locality of reference. To address this issue, an alternative was to consider storing data container as “structure of array” while keeping its interface look like an “array of structures”.
- It was also expected to have a ROOT-friendly data format, using at most only a small part of the ATLAS code base. Also, a desirable feature was to be able to read only parts of objects as needed and allow the user analysis code to extend the data stored for an object.

The result of this redesign exercise was xAOD, a new data format that offers efficient data access and is readable from both Athena and the ROOT framework. The following section describes the key features of its implementation.

2.5 The Auxiliary Data Store

The ATLAS offline software uses the Whiteboard [46] pattern. This pattern allows specifying the operations on the data as a sequence of algorithms with implicit dependencies. Hence, the algorithms do not directly depend on each other, but rather

FIGURE 2.3: Auxiliary Store Overview [28]

fetch and commit data from a central event store called the Auxiliary Data Store. The event store holds objects of arbitrary types each one identified by a string key. Algorithms use keys to retrieve/store the data from/to the data store. The rest of this section follows Krasznahorkay [28] and Buckley [6], to describe some use cases of the ATLAS event store for data analysis.

The event store objects are split into two categories as below:

- **Interface objects:** These provide a user interface for a particular data type, but do not contain actual data.
- **Payload objects:** These contain the actual data held by the Auxiliary Data Store. Payload objects are accessed and modified through the Interface objects.

As shown in figure 2.3, all physics objects implement their corresponding public interfaces. These interfaces provide generic functionality common for a given category. For example, all particle classes derive from `xAOD::IParticle` interface. However, in order to benefit from the features of the auxiliary store, they are also derived from a common base class `SG::AuxElement`. The `AuxElement` class provides most of the functionality necessary for auxiliary storage. This includes a mechanism of `Accessors` and `Decorators` used to access and extend data variables using their string keys. These keys are internally mapped with integers for fast lookup. The `Accessor` class caches this lookup, so it does not need to be done each time the variable is accessed.

Both the interfaces and payload objects support two usage scenarios. The objects can be individually accessed as stand-alone instances, or they can be associated with container objects to represent collections. The user can associate a stand-alone object with a stand-alone auxiliary store or a collection of objects with an auxiliary container. Referring to figure 2.3 a stand-alone interface implements `SG::AuxElement` and its corresponding auxiliary store implements `xAOD::AuxInfoBase`. Similarly, the container interface implements `DataVector<T>` and its corresponding auxiliary store implements `xAOD::AuxContainerBase`. The EDM provides multiple types of auxiliary containers to support common analysis use cases. It is the auxiliary container that manages the persistent storage structure, and contiguous memory layout. This separation of interface from the real data offers the following benefits:

- The interface provides a consistent method of access which is independent of storage technology. This abstraction hides the complexity of I/O operations

FIGURE 2.4: Container covariance of DataVector [28]

from user code and allows multiple implementations based on storage technology, without affecting the user code.

- The payload objects separately store static and dynamic variables, while they are accessed through a standard interface using their string keys. This separation allows addition or removal of dynamic variables without changing data format. Thus, users can add/remove variables to/from the containers at the run-time during the analysis.
- It allows access to partial information about objects during analysis.

2.5.1 The DataVector

The interface objects referred above can either represent stand-alone objects or collections. A frequent use case is to iterate over vectors of physics objects and read/modify their properties. To support this, a usual C++ `std::vector<T>` like interface is provided by a special type – `DataVector<T>`, [3] which delegates the data access requests to an associated auxiliary container. In addition to an iterable interface, it supports following features to form the foundation for its usage along with auxiliary containers.

- **Optional ownership:** The user can choose if the `DataVector` should own the elements to which it points. In such case, these elements are deleted when they are erased from the vector.
- **Container covariance:** It is a useful inheritance relation for analyzing collections of physics objects. For example, as shown in Figure 2.4, if a type `Particle` inherits from another type `FourVector`, then by virtue of container covariance, `DataVector<Particle>` also derives from `DataVector<FourVector>`. This facilitates writing generic algorithms simply referring to base class interfaces.
- **Auxiliary Data:** Arbitrary types of data can be attached to elements of a `DataVector`. These data are stored as vectors and managed by a separate ‘auxiliary store’ object, which can be accessed by an abstract interface as shown in figure 2.3. These data variables may be either static or dynamic and are stored by separate static or dynamic auxiliary stores. Figure 2.5 shows an example of xAOD data file. Every xAOD file stores event data in a tree structure with a default name “`CollectionTree`”. This tree contains one or more interface containers and their associated auxiliary containers. Static auxiliary containers hold all properties of element type known at the time of class definition and are suffixed with “`Aux.`” On the other hand, the dynamic auxiliary containers hold the data

FIGURE 2.5: An example of xAOD file [28]

FIGURE 2.6: A particle object as SG: AuxElement [28]

added during run-time and are suffixed with “AuxDyn.”. Typically, dynamic variables represent the derived properties which do not need to be saved into files for storage optimization. Another usage of the dynamic container is to add/remove additional information – decorations. (e.g., Temporary variables or reusable results of expensive computations)

Figure 2.6 shows a concrete example of the features described above. In this case, `xAOD::Muon` implements the interface `xAOD::IParticle`. This inheritance ensures that tools and algorithms can safely access all Muon objects through a consistent `IParticle` interface. Furthermore, as `IParticle` inherits `SG::AuxElement`, every Muon object automatically becomes compatible with auxiliary containers. Thus users can decorate them with additional variables, remove selected variables at run-time or access partial information as needed.

2.5.2 ElementLinks

Most often, physics objects need to be used by multiple collections. Given the large sizes of data sets, it follows that saving multiple instances of such objects would be impractical, both concerning memory usage and disk space. The usual solution is to use C++ pointers to maintain associative relationships across multiple containers. However, to save such links to disk, EDM provides a persistable smart pointer type named `ElementLink<T>`. This type holds two numbers. The first one identifies the

FIGURE 2.7: Transient view of persistent storage layout.
Following Buckley [6]

container of the target object and the second one stores the index of the target in its container. For example, all calorimeter clusters and all inner-detector track particles are kept into their container, while electrons have element links to a cluster and a track-particle in those containers.

2.5.3 Transient view of persistent storage layout

This feature makes the physical “structure of arrays” look like, “arrays of structures”. Figure 2.7 shows an example of a static auxiliary container holding `xAOD::Electron` elements. Each `Electron` object has static properties which are interpreted by user code as class members. Thus, in memory, the `DataVector` looks like a simple array of `Electron` objects. It holds a reference to an auxiliary container and delegates all access requests to the auxiliary container. The auxiliary container stores these variables as vectors of fundamental data types. This layout gives a better spatial locality during traversal of these variables.

Furthermore, the columnar form of auxiliary container simplifies I/O operations, as its layout matches the ROOT’s persistent storage layout (section: 3.2.1). In addition, the storage of each variable as a separate vector facilitates partial reading of data. This separation allows the analyst to retrieve an entire vector of only a few selected variables without loading the entire event data.

2.6 Methods of accessing Auxiliary Containers

This section follows Krasznahorkay [28] and Buckley [6], to describe available types of auxiliary containers and their key features to support common use cases. As discussed later in chapter 4, this work is scoped to support the first method described below. However, the rest of these methods are considered to be future use cases. Hence, they are studied as inputs for setting the design objectives.

FIGURE 2.8: Auxiliary Store: Static Container.
Following Buckley [6]

2.6.1 Read access

This is the most common use case where the user reads data from a file and uses it for histograms or N-tuple creation. Figure 2.8 shows an example of a static auxiliary container suitable for such usage. When a container is read from a file, the I/O system de-serializes it into an auxiliary container object and associates it with the DataVector. This association prepares the DataVector to access the auxiliary store via the abstract interface IAuxStore. The auxiliary container manages a separate vector for each variable. When the analysis code requests access to a variable of an element, the DataVector retrieves the corresponding variable vector from the auxiliary container, then uses that element's index to return the actual variable. Each variable vector is allocated with contiguous memory space. This provides better locality of reference and simplifies I/O operations, as the entire static auxiliary container is stored/restored as a single object.

2.6.2 Decorations

This method allows the addition of new variables into const containers. Figure 2.9 shows such usage with a dynamic auxiliary container. The static auxiliary container holds a reference to a dynamic auxiliary container which manages all additional variable vectors. The static store serves the requests to access only static variables. For dynamic variables, it forwards all the access and variable addition requests to the dynamic store.

2.6.3 Deep copy

This is particularly useful when a new container with the same variables as an existing one is required, but only for a subset of objects or events passing some selection criteria. As the DataVector provides all functionality of `std::vector<T>`, the analyst can create a new instance of an interface container and associate it with a new auxiliary store. The elements of existing containers can just be copied to the new container.

FIGURE 2.9: Auxiliary Store: Dynamic Container.
Following Buckley [6]

FIGURE 2.10: Auxiliary Store: Shallow Copy Container.
Following Buckley [6]

2.6.4 Shallow copy

Deep copies of entire containers are usually impractical due to large memory footprints. Shallow copies are particularly useful for applying some modification to all objects of a container but only for few selected variables. This is accomplished by a special auxiliary store implementation – `ShallowAuxContainer`. Figure 2.10 shows an example of such a use case. The `ShallowAuxContainer` holds a reference to the original container so that it can share the space of unchanged variables, eliminating the need for copy. It also maintains an internal auxiliary dynamic container. When a modification of a variable is requested, the internal auxiliary store makes the copy of the original variable vector and applies the change to the copied vector. This defers the copy operation until the variable is modified. Similarly, the decoration request is also handled by the internal auxiliary store by adding a new variable vector. During the simple read access, the request is first handled by `ShallowAuxContainer`. If the requested variable is not present in the `ShallowAuxContainer` then the request is forwarded to the original `AuxContainer`.

2.6.5 Transient-only read access

Often the collection of objects need some application of algorithms without the need for modification or storage of data. The EDM provides a special class named `ConstDataVector` to accomplish this efficiently. This type does not own its elements and holds only pointers. Thus, it is the most efficient alternative for STL like usages such as sorting and searching.

The topics covered in this chapter, specifically the ATLAS EDM and the Auxiliary Store, are used as the building blocks for the `DataSource` functionality. Chapter 4 describes the usage of these features for the data access within the ATLAS analyses.

Chapter 3

The ROOT Data Analysis Framework

ROOT [2] is an object-oriented framework for solving a wide range of data analysis problems. It provides basic utilities and services such as I/O and graphics, as well as a rich set of tools, algorithms and data structures. Physicists can use these modules as building blocks of their analysis code. The ability of ROOT to efficiently handle large datasets and features like Python interface layer – PyROOT [37], command line interpreter, parallel processing and a wide range of physics analysis libraries make it a primary choice for HEP Software. As discussed in chapter 2, the ATLAS EDM uses ROOT file format for storing xAOD data sets. Therefore, its I/O framework and the file structure are of specific interest for the ATLAS analysis framework. This chapter covers an overview of ROOT’s I/O system and then describes its new analysis interface – RDataFrame. This introduction prepares a background about some key features of RDataFrame and ROOT’s I/O, as the building blocks used for this work. In particular, the chapter 4 describes how the design and implementation of this work rely on the RDataFrame interface. The chapter 5 describes the significance of ROOT’s I/O features on the performance optimization of this prototype.

3.1 The ROOT File

The ROOT file is analogous to a UNIX file directory. It contains arbitrary levels of sub-directories and objects stored in a machine-independent ASCII [65] format. This section follows ROOT User’s Guide [44] to briefly describe its physical layout as stored to disk and its logical view as exposed to analysis code.

3.1.1 Physical Layout

Figure 3.1 shows an example output of `TFile::Map` function call from ROOT’s interactive session. The `Map` function lists the contents of the file in a sequence they are physically stored on disk. The output columns represent date/time, the start address of the record, the number of bytes in the record, the class name of the record and the compression factor.

Every file begins with a file header which holds metadata such as file format version, Zip compression level and some bookkeeping information about data records and their pointers. In this example, the first record has the start address at 100, as the file header occupies first 100 bytes. The first record represents `TFile` object which is the in-memory representation of the file. Several objects containing the analysis data then follow this sequence. This particular example shows 15 histograms stored by instances of the `TH1F` class. The entire ROOT framework provides a large number of

```

root[] f.Map()
20051208/124502 At:100 N=114 TFile
20051208/124502 At:214 N=413 TH1F CX = 2.35
20051208/124502 At:627 N=410 TH1F CX = 2.36
20051208/124502 At:1037 N=396 TH1F CX = 2.45
20051208/124502 At:1433 N=400 TH1F CX = 2.42
20051208/124502 At:1833 N=402 TH1F CX = 2.41
20051208/124502 At:2235 N=416 TH1F CX = 2.33
20051208/124502 At:2651 N=406 TH1F CX = 2.39
20051208/124502 At:3057 N=403 TH1F CX = 2.40
20051208/124502 At:3460 N=411 TH1F CX = 2.36
20051208/124502 At:3871 N=400 TH1F CX = 2.42
20051208/124502 At:4271 N=409 TH1F CX = 2.38
20051208/124502 At:4680 N=409 TH1F CX = 2.38
20051208/124502 At:5089 N=420 TH1F CX = 2.32
20051208/124502 At:5509 N=406 TH1F CX = 2.40
20051208/124502 At:5915 N=405 TH1F CX = 2.40
20051208/124503 At:6320 N=3052 StreamerInfo CX = 3.16
20051208/124503 At:9372 N=732 KeysList
20051208/124503 At:10104 N=53 FreeSegments
20051208/124503 At:10157 N=1 END

```

FIGURE 3.1: Physical Layout of a ROOT File
Source: ROOT Users Guide [44]

such classes covering a wide range of analysis objects.

The analysis data records are then followed by the `StreamerInfo` record. The `StreamerInfo` contains a list of descriptions of all classes which are written to the file. For a complete description of a class, all its ancestors and object data members are also described recursively. The ROOT type system uses this information to resolve the C++ class type for de-serializing objects from the file. The last three records include the list of keys, the list of free segments, and an address indicating the end of data.

3.1.2 Logical View

In general, when the file is de-serialized into an in-memory object, the analysis code may need to access parts of its data in an arbitrarily random pattern. ROOT provides the `TKey` class to support such query access. The `TKey` class allows identification of an object by a string representation called as “key.” Thus, a reference to an object can be acquired passing the name of its key to the `TFile::Get` function. The `KeysList` referred in above example provides a linked list interface. Thus, the collection of keys can be iterated over to access corresponding objects. The `TTree` class in combination with `TKeys` thus provides a mechanism to access the data in a logical sequence, irrespective of their physical storage order in the file. The last record in this example, `FreeSegments` represents the list of free blocks available in the file. This information is used to recycle the freed up space. While saving an object into the file, ROOT first tries to find the best free block. If a free block matches the size of the new object, it writes the object in that block and removes its record from the `FreeSegments` list. If the size of the object does not match any of the available free blocks, then ROOT uses the first available free block in the file sequence which is bigger than the object.

FIGURE 3.2: Column-wise layout of TTree data in memory buffers
Source: ROOT Users Guide [44]

3.2 The ROOT I/O Framework

The ROOT I/O framework provides the necessary foundation to handle low-level features such as data exchange with file system through serialization and compression. Libraries and analysis codes heavily rely on these features for frequent use cases. The I/O system abstracts away the complexity of I/O operations from the analysis tools and libraries. This section follows Antcheva [2] and Guilherme [21], to describe some essential features of this framework.

3.2.1 Column-Wise Storage

A frequent use case for data access in HEP software is selective, sparse scanning of the data. The access to conventional, horizontally partitioned data requires that entire event to be loaded in memory, thereby preventing partial access. ROOT resolves this difficulty by using vertical partitioning. The TTree class provides the necessary implementation to represent transient data as a tree which is partitioned into branches. Thus, each branch becomes independently accessible. The TBranch class provides implementation to store consecutive collections of objects. Furthermore, there exists an option to store the entire object into a branch or to split up into sub-branches of individual data members. This feature is referred to as splitting. A complex object with nested data members represents a tree with top level branches referring to its immediate data members. The recursive splitting of these branches decomposes a tree with arbitrary depth until each leaf contains an individual data member.

The column-wise storage uses the above-referred splitting feature. The event data is interpreted as a table, with events represented along rows and data members along columns. The splitting feature automates the creation of these columns. Figure 3.2 shows an example of this mapping. In this case, the tree contains two top-level objects A and B with nested data members. The figure shows the effect of first level splitting, which creates a column-wise layout of the same objects in the memory buffer.

The column-wise layout minimizes the I/O operations and the volume of transferred data because it reads only the required branches of each object and leaves all unused members initialized by the default constructor. When iterating over collections, this layout arranges the data members to be consecutive on the storage medium. This contiguous layout allows block-wise reading of the data for several events in one go, thereby improving I/O efficiency.

3.2.2 Serialization

The storage of C++ objects requires that the I/O system should know a complete type description referred to as the Dictionary of the object. ROOT provides a dictionary for all its classes and also provides a mechanism for users to build dictionaries for custom classes. The type description data referred to as Reflection contains the location of data members in memory, their size and necessary storage pattern. ROOT uses this information to serialize and de-serialize arbitrary data via automatically generated object streamers. The reflection information is stored along with the data. This association eliminates the strong dependency of custom libraries. In particular, the data which is written to the file using a custom user library can be successfully read back using reflection information, even without the presence of the user library.

3.2.3 Compression

During the serialization, ROOT compresses the data to reduce the storage space and the I/O bandwidth usage. However, this is associated with a cost of slightly increased CPU time when reading and writing files. ROOT uses a compression algorithm based on the `gzip` algorithm. It supports nine levels of compression with default level set to one. The compression can be disabled by setting this level to zero. The optimum level depends on the type and sparsity of the data because it is the trade-off between read/write efficiency and the disk space savings.

3.2.4 Basket Clustering

Typical read access of the file follows three steps – reading buffers from file, decompression, and de-serialization. Similarly, writing to the file follows reverse sequence – serialization, compression and writing buffers to the file. The compression usually happens branch-wise, using benefits of splitting. Each branch has a memory buffer object called the `TBasket`. When the data is added to `TTree` using `TTree::Fill`, all relevant objects are copied into these baskets. Once the basket is full, it is compressed and then written to the file.

Since the basket represents the smallest unit of compression, it is desirable to have a contiguous layout of baskets to ensure uninterrupted read patterns. In general,

FIGURE 3.3: RDataFrame Overview

Source: E. Guiraud, ROOT Users Workshop 2018 [23]

having all baskets of the same size defeats this purpose because the density of data may influence the frequency of writing the basket from branch to branch. For example, a branch containing one integer per event and having a basket size of 32KB will write a basket to disk every 8000 events. Whereas a branch with events containing a collection greater than 32KB will write a basket for every event. Thus, the contents of a single event with many varying-sized branches may be spread throughout a file. ROOT resolves this difficulty using adaptive basket size. The `TTree::OptimizeBaskets` function attempts to automatically resize the basket such that each branch basket holds the same number of events and reduce the total memory usage.

In addition, the `TTree` uses the `AutoFlush` feature to periodically flush the baskets to disk, creating a `Cluster` of baskets. After a file is created and a given amount of data is buffered, all baskets are compressed and flushed to disk. This offers two benefits. First, the cluster provides a larger chunk of data to be loaded by a single read. Secondly, this allows parallel de-compression [21] and de-serialization as multiple baskets from a single cluster can be concurrently processed by multiple threads. The `TBufferMerger` [21] further extends these benefits to reconstruction workflow using parallel compression and parallel serialization while writing data to files.

3.3 The RDataFrame Interface

As concluded in section 1.4, ROOT6 made significant framework upgrades aimed at data analysis challenges and goals on HL-LHC timeline. The support for Just-in-Time compilation and implicit parallelism are the two major features which provided the necessary foundation for several user interface features and performance enhancements in later releases. Built on top of these features, ROOT v6.14 introduced a new component – `RDataFrame` [38], aiming at an expressive and easy to use interface while implementing implicit performance optimizations. This section follows Guiraud [23] and `RDataFrame` documentation [38] to describe some key features of this interface.

Figure 3.3 shows an overview of `RDataFrame`'s role within a typical analysis. This particular example shows a minimalist use case of a range filter to slice the data by event indices and the definition of a custom column `myvar`. `RDataFrame` interprets the dataset as a table, where rows represent events and columns represent definitions of data variables. It reads data from a suitable source and allows the analysis code to define new variables as custom columns. This definition is general enough

to create an arbitrary number of columns using arbitrary data types. Furthermore, the new variable can be a function of one or more existing columns, or a user-defined function taking external parameters. The analysis code can further apply range filters, or user-defined cuts/filters for slicing or slimming this data before creating analysis results such as histograms, profiles, and cut-flow reports. The results can be saved into ROOT file or used for user-defined operations.

There are currently multiple options available to perform the data analysis, which include `TTreeReader` [61], `TSelector` within PROOF [36] environment, PyROOT [37] and some experiment-specific implementations such as ATLAS EventLoop/AnaAlgorithm [1]. The inherent variance of tool/experiment-specific interfaces, however, makes the analysis code context dependent. Switching tools, data source or even the execution environment needs significant updates in the code.

Another difficulty stems from the level of implementation details. In particular, achieving the effective level of parallelism is usually not trivial, as the analysis code usually needs to know implementation details of tool/framework and the execution environment. `RDataFrame` offers to resolve these difficulties by hiding the complexity of the event-loop behind the abstract interface. The interface attempts to separate the physics analysis features from performance tuning features. Thus, the analyst declares “what” to analyze and ROOT chooses “how” to execute it efficiently within the available environment. `RDataFrame` implements this through two important aspects, namely Declarative/Functional Programming and Implicit Parallelism.

FIGURE 3.4: RDataFrame execution graph
Source: E. Guiraud, ROOT Users Workshop 2018 [23]

3.3.1 Declarative/Functional Programming

In order to let the analyst focus on physics analysis, RDataFrame organizes the analysis code into three basic steps, namely define Transforms, apply Actions and generate Results. Figure 3.4 shows a simple example of this workflow. In this case, the first line creates a new instance of RDataFrame which takes ownership of the dataset. The analyst then applies a filter on variable 'x'. Note that, the parameter is passed to the filter as a string literal. This is possible due to ROOT's type system utilizing the Just-In-Time compilation feature as referred above. The second line defines a new variable 'r2' as a function of existing variables 'x' and 'y'. The returned value of these definitions, 'df2' is also a data frame. Thus, it allows further definitions or transforms using the same interface. The last two lines of this example create the histogram and graph respectively. The sequence of these definitions precisely declares the data dependencies between transient results as shown by the graph.

RDataFrame supports a wide range of Transforms, Actions and Results. In addition to standard pre-defined actions, users can also apply generic actions to execute arbitrary code. This is accomplished by `Foreach` and `ForeachSlot` functions. The `Foreach(f, columnList)`, takes a function 'f' and executes it on columns specified by 'columnList'. However, in this case users are expected to provide a thread-safe implementation for user-defined action. The `ForeachSlot`, function helps under such situations, by providing a 'slot' parameter, which the user code can use for thread-safe implementation. Other features include named filters which can be used for cut-flow reports. The data frame also supports range based transforms, and a snapshot feature to write the processed data to files. Appendix B lists all features currently supported by RDataFrame.

The declarative programming aspect of this interface abstracts away the complexity and improves readability of the analysis while the functional programming aspect minimizes the functional dependencies across the operations. This wraps slices of the user code into individual nodes of a function graph. Each node can be safely executed as a small reusable component, independent of other nodes and external states. Solving such nodes as pure functions minimizes the side effects of the shared state which is especially important for correctness and thread-safety.

The abstraction of the interface improves the portability of the analysis. First, the reproducibility of analysis results using a different data source does not need major changes to the analysis code as the data frame transparently supports multiple data sources. In the future, the number of supported data sources can be safely assumed to grow. Secondly, switching between different execution environments, from stand-alone laptop to high-end multi-core desktops or clusters, does not need any changes in the analysis.

The portability also applies to the choice of language. The same interface is made available in PyROOT via Python bindings. This allows analysts to choose the language based on specific needs of physics groups without changing the code beyond few syntactical updates.

3.3.2 Implicit Parallelism

`RDataFrame` uses implicit parallelism to boost the performance of the analysis code. The analysis code needs to invoke the `ROOT::EnableImplicitMT` [43] function before construction of the data frame. This function informs ROOT to initialize the underlying task scheduling mechanism and enable thread-safety features. The rest of the analysis code does not need any other configuration for parallelism. Once enabled, the `ImplicitMT` feature allows `RDataFrame` to transparently run the event-loop in parallel using multiple threads and apply implicit optimizations.

In general, the analysis code may contain an arbitrary number of transforms, actions, and results, with complex dependencies. However, the data frame ensures to run the event-loop only once. This is accomplished by deferring the actual evaluation of action until the analysis code accesses its result. These actions are called lazy actions. For example, referring to figure 3.4, the declaration of the histogram and the graph are both lazy actions. Thus, their evaluation is deferred until their values are accessed by callers. Consequently, this triggers the event-loop only after the first access to any of the lazy actions. Once the event-loop is triggered, the data frame solves the function call graph for each event. This updates the results of all nodes in the call graph. This configuration ensures that the event-loop is executed only once and that each action is performed exactly once and delayed until its result is used. It is therefore recommended to declare all the transforms and actions before accessing their results.

The data frame uses a set of threads to execute sub-ranges of events concurrently. Each worker thread processes a distinct sub-range. This isolation implicitly ensures the synchronization, thereby eliminating the need for explicit protection of sub-ranges for thread safety. The data frame provides a pure functional implementation for `Define` and `Filter` actions, such that they have no side effects and they do not depend on any global state. Thus, they are inherently thread-safe. In addition, all actions are built to be thread-safe with the exception of `ForEach`, where users need to provide a thread-safe implementation.

FIGURE 3.5: RDataFrame Task Based Parallelism
Source: E. Guiraud, ROOT Users Workshop 2018 [23]

3.3.3 Task Scheduling

For parallel execution of event-loop, RDataFrame uses Intel Threading Building Blocks [40](TBB), for task scheduling and thread-pool management. Figure 3.5 shows an overview of this configuration. The data frame splits the entire event range into several sub-ranges. Each sub-range is treated as an independent task that can be concurrently processed along with other tasks. After completion of the event-loop, the partial results available on all threads are merged to form the final result.

RDataFrame relies on TBB for scheduling of tasks. The activation of the `ImplicitMT` feature triggers the necessary initialization of threads depending on available hardware configuration. TBB uses task-based parallelism for scheduling threads. This interpretation of parallelism in terms of tasks rather than threads has multiple advantages. The optimization efforts and performance profiling observations discussed later in chapter 5 are based on common performance issues addressed by task-based parallelism [40] as outlined below:

1. **Over-Subscription:** The “subscription” in this context refers to the mapping of a *logical thread* created by a threading package to a *physical thread* of the hardware. The highest efficiency usually occurs when there is one running logical thread per physical thread. Any deviation from this implies the possibility of one of two types of inefficiencies. The first case is due to the insufficient number of logical threads which under-utilize the available physical threads, referred to as Under-subscription. The second case is due to more logical threads than physical threads, which leads to a time-sliced execution of logical threads, referred to as Over-Subscription. The TBB Task Scheduler prevents Under-Subscription as well as Over-Subscription by managing its thread-pool and letting the user create tasks instead of threads. Throughout the execution, the scheduler maintains one logical thread per physical thread regardless of the number of tasks. This approach also has a performance benefit. A task in TBB is a much lighter object compared to a thread. Starting and terminating task is significantly efficient than that of a logical thread which makes the implementation scalable to large number tasks.
2. **Fair Scheduling:** General purpose operating systems allocate the time-slices to their threads based on the concept of *Fair Scheduling*. The fair distribution provides an equal time slice to each logical thread. Each thread is preempted

periodically out of concern that some large tasks will dominate others. Although this is the safest strategy for operating systems, it incurs some inefficiencies due to unnecessary context switching overheads. TBB, on the other hand, knows some task level information. Thus the task scheduler can sacrifice fairness for efficiency and let the tasks complete without interruptions. In particular, the scheduler takes care of differences in task loads by monitoring processors and starting new tasks on idle processors. For keeping the tasks to optimal, it uses recursive splitting of tasks to an optimum level of granularity. Users can configure the depth of this splitting by choosing the task implementation best suited for the application. The fine granularity works better in combination with the dynamic load balancing as described below. The overall result is more efficient execution of tasks due to the *Unfair Scheduling*.

3. **Load Imbalance** With thread-based programming, the user is often required to deal with the load balancing. A general solution to achieve an optimal load balance is usually tricky. Thinking the workload in terms of tasks, rather than threads resolves this difficulty by deferring the actual allocation of a task to run time. TBB allows the user to configure tasks, preferably a large number of small-sized tasks. It then schedules the available tasks to idle threads using the task stealing approach. Once a thread completes its task, it dynamically gets a new task. Thus given that the user ensures sufficiently fine granularity, all threads remain busy throughout the application execution.

This dynamic balancing scales well with the number of processors due to the emphasis on data-parallel programming. In a thread-based approach, a program is split up into separate functional blocks, each one assigned to a thread. This split-up does not scale with the number of processors, as the number of functional blocks are typically fixed. In contrast, the data-parallel approach splits the data into a large number of tasks. This split-up scales much better with the increasing number of processors, because the fine granularity along with the dynamic scheduling implies that there would always be a large number of tasks available for more processors.

3.3.4 Experiment-specific Usage

The task-based parallelism referred above assumes that when a thread is ready to process an event, all the necessary data required by the function call graph is also ready for access. Such an assumption is practical only in case of tabular data formats, where event data can be simply accessed as a row of values. In general, this is not trivial to handle due to complex data structures defined by experiments, and dependencies of data elements within the event. `RDataaFrame` resolves this difficulty by delegating the responsibility of data access to experiment-specific implementations. This is accomplished through `ROOT::RDataaSource` interface. The experiments/third-party libraries using arbitrary data types can provide implementations of `RDataaSource` to be compliant with `RDataaFrame`. Some recent implementations include the Apache Arrow data source: `RArrowDS` [42], and LHCb data source: `RMDFDS` [22]. This work aims to extend this concept to ATLAS xAOD format. The rest of this thesis applies the above-referred topics to the ATLAS experiment-specific usage of `RDataaFrame`.

Chapter 4

xAOD Data Source

This chapter describes the design and implementation of the xAOD Data Source. The initial implementation of this prototype is aimed at evaluating the usage of the latest features of the ROOT framework for optimization of ATLAS analyses. As described in chapter 2, the ATLAS EDM provides a set of interfaces and implementations for efficient data access and supports a wide range of analysis use cases. Thus, the ATLAS event store interface – TEvent class is a particularly interesting component for standalone ROOT based analyses. Furthermore, as concluded in chapter 3, the RDataFrame interface offers a rich set of features to improve the analysis code, both in terms of performance and usability. This prototype aims to establish a link between the ATLAS event store and RDataFrame. The chapter begins with an overview of design principles and patterns applied in this work. It then documents the scope of the prototype, followed by a design overview. The key implementation features of all classes and their interactions are discussed with an execution sequence. The chapter concludes with the process followed for verification and validation of the implementation.

4.1 Design Principles and Patterns

This section follows R. Martin [30] and E. Gamma [18] to introduce the principles and patterns referred during this chapter. The motivation comes from the architectural requirements, in particular, maintainability and re-usability. The rest of this chapter uses these principles and patterns to describe the objectives which steered the design and implementation of this prototype.

4.1.1 Software Design Principles

With the growing complexities and continual changes in the requirements, it is often observed that software maintenance becomes gradually difficult as more features are added. This difficulty stems from the undesirable traits of software design which are usually difficult to detect and measure. Some of these symptoms referred to as “code smells” include *rigidity*, *fragility*, and *viscosity*. Rigidity makes it difficult to modify an existing feature. Fragility makes the code easy to break, even in case of small changes. Viscosity makes it difficult to add a new feature without complicating the overall design. The design principles provide a critical view to identifying possible sources of such code smells. This approach is followed from the beginning of this work considering the requirement that the prototype is eventually expected to support real-world use cases in the production environment. Following Martin [30], the relevant principles considered during this activity are outlined below:

1. **Single Responsibility Principle [33] (SRP):**

This principle states that a class should have only one reason to change. This statement aims at the cohesion of the software. A cohesive software unit contains only the minimalist set of functionality. Concretely, any implementation feature, which does not address the requirements of a given class, should not belong to that class.

Given that the requirements continually change, each functional requirement is treated as a reason to change the class. Each class should have only one such reason. If a class has more than one responsibility, the associated requirements are coupled. Changes to one of these requirements may impair the class's ability to meet others. This constraint increases the rigidity.

Furthermore, the functions of the class are expected to obey certain pre/postconditions. It becomes difficult to fulfill all such conditions when one of the coupled functionality changes. This difficulty increases the fragility. The proper application of SRP keeps each class decoupled from other classes, allowing it to evolve independently.

A particular example of SRP is `SG::AuxElement` class as discussed in section 2.5.1. Referring to figure 2.6 the `xAOD::Muon_v1` supports the functionality of a physical particle. However, in order to comply with the auxiliary store, it also needs to support the functionality of data access, which is unrelated to its particle interface. This responsibility is handled by `SG::AuxElement` class. This separation makes the `Muon` responsible only for the physics related functionality. Any changes in the functional requirements of the auxiliary store would not affect the `Muon` or any other particles implementing `IParticle` interface.

2. **Open/Closed Principle [32] (OCP):**

This principle states that the software entities (classes, modules, functions, etc.) should be open for extension but closed for modification. This statement aims at extensible design by minimizing logical dependencies. When a single change in a program results in a cascade of changes to other dependent modules, the design hints about rigidity. In such cases, the OCP advises that the system should be refactored such that similar changes in the future would not need a change of the existing structure. If the OCP is correctly applied, the future changes of a similar kind are achieved by adding new code, not by changing the existing code that already works. Thus, the existing code remains open for extension but closed for modification.

As an example of OCP, the above-referred `Muon` class can be revisited. In this case, the `IParticle` interface ensures the application of OCP. This interface provides the infrastructure to inherit the functionality of auxiliary storage and allows physicists to derive new particles. Thus, the framework is open for new functionality without the need for changing existing code.

3. **Dependency Inversion Principle [31] (DIP):**

This principle states that abstractions should not depend upon details. Details should depend upon abstractions. In this context, the term "detail" refers to any concrete element of the implementation such as derived classes, functions

or variables holding application-specific values. The statement of DIP emphasizes the purpose of abstraction to decouple the dependencies across the modules. If an abstract class knows about the implementation details of its derived class, it makes the abstraction constrained to a specific implementation. Such a dependency makes the abstraction difficult to reuse in other contexts, which defeats the original purpose of abstraction.

For example, consider two classes with a client-server relationship. If the server depends on concrete details of the client, it makes the server unsuitable for reuse with other client implementations in future. In such cases, the DIP advises that both the client and server should depend on an abstract interface that defines the minimal functionality that must be supported by each client. The server can then use this interface irrespective of the type of client. This decoupling makes the server reusable and allows both the client and the server to evolve independently.

4.1.2 Software Design Patterns

The design pattern catalogs represent the documentation of experience and knowledge gained from successful object-oriented solutions from the past. In this context, each pattern identifies a class of recurring design problem and recommends possible alternatives for its solution. The description of the pattern also includes remarks on the consequences of a particular solution and possible trade-offs which may influence the implementation. This identification helps software developers to detect critical features of the problem and evaluate the design alternatives. In addition, the standard names allocated to these patterns form a consistent design vocabulary. This standardization helps the developers to communicate and document the design solutions with the focus on design intent rather than implementation details. This section follows Gamma [18] to briefly introduce the design patterns used in this chapter.

1. Adapter [17]:

The Adapter pattern helps to integrate the classes with incompatible interfaces. A frequent use case which leads to such a requirement is the use of external libraries. The interfaces provided by external packages are usually incompatible with internal packages even though they implement similar functionality. In such cases, the adapter class provides a common interface to its client and encapsulates the function calls to external packages referred to as Adaptee. The client requests its calls to the adapter, which in turn invokes the specific implementation from the Adaptee. This configuration hides the interface of adaptee from the client and allows it to work with arbitrary adaptees without knowing their interfaces.

As described in section 3.3.4, the `RDataaFrame` interface relies on the `RDataaSource` interface for interacting with arbitrary data sources. In this context, the `RDataaSource` provides the common Adapter interface to its client `RDataaFrame`. The experiment-specific libraries are encapsulated by corresponding data sources which implement the `RDataaSource` interface. Section 4.6 describes how this work implements an adapter between `RDataaFrame` and the ATLAS event store.

2. Template Method [19]:

This pattern defines an abstract skeleton of an algorithm. The algorithm defines some implementation itself and defers few steps to derived classes. This abstraction allows the derived classes to redefine those sub-steps to have an application-specific variant of the algorithm. This pattern hides the implementation details of derived classes from the abstract algorithm and allows the derived classes to have multiple versions of an algorithm without changing its structure. Hence, this pattern is an application of *Dependency-Inversion Principle*.

The `RDataSource` interface defines an algorithm sequence for execution of event-loop. The experiment-specific data sources provide the implementation for some of its sub-steps. Section 4.5 describes how this work provides the ATLAS specific implementation of this pattern.

4.2 Scope of the Prototype

This prototype is scoped to achieve at least one proof-of-concept implementation that facilitates correct and stable execution of some common analysis use cases. Given the thesis timeline, this activity is set to demonstrate basic building blocks of a typical data analysis workflow. Concretely, this includes reading data from xAOD files, filtering a subset of events, applying cuts/transforms to the filtered data, and producing histograms for validation. The data access is considered to be read-only throughout, thus in-place modifications or decorations of analysis objects, and writing the output data to files is currently left beyond the scope. Furthermore, it is assumed that the execution environment is a standalone laptop/desktop and the data is locally available.

4.3 Design objectives

Apart from the correctness and stability, the two primary motivation factors discussed in section 1.4, namely "**Analysis Execution Time**" and "**Analysis Development Time**" remain as key priorities. To this end, multiple design objectives are considered as outlined below:

4.3.1 Scalability

The `RDataFrame` interface already uses the `ImplicitMT` feature to boost the performance of the analysis code exploiting available hardware threads. At the minimum, the data source should not introduce any noticeable "Serial Component" of the code, thereby ensuring the best possible scalability.

4.3.2 Minimal Abstraction Overhead

Introduction of any new abstraction layer into an existing low-level framework is expected to follow C++'s *Zero Overhead Principle* [50]. This applies both in terms of time and space. However, this does not mean zero cost. Rather it implies: (a) Don't pay for what you don't use. (b) When you do use it, the overhead must be justifiable by the effectiveness of the abstraction. Therefore, objects are preferred to be

constructed and initialized just before they are actually used. In addition, attempts are made to keep object lifespans as short as possible.

4.3.3 Modularity

The scope of the prototyping phase obviously limits the complexity of use cases. However, the design is expected to survive real-world use cases after the prototyping phase. This implies adaptability to new/changed requirements in the near future. Therefore, interfaces are designed with the focus on object orientation, following the *Single Responsibility Principle*(section: 4.1.1) for each interface so that each class serves exactly one purpose and delegates any additional responsibilities to other classes via suitable association. This allows each class to evolve independently as more features are added to support future requirements.

The modularity is also attempted in structure. To this end, complex classes are built using composition of simpler classes. This allows to easily replace the slices of implementation by their alternatives as and when needed. Wherever possible, the standard STL algorithms and data structures are preferred over a custom implementation. This approach has multiple benefits. First, these pre-validated/optimized components are easily replaceable without the need for low-level (re)testing. Secondly, their standardized interfaces improve the readability of code. In addition, the performance improvements from the future updates of the standard, are transparently conveyed to the analyzer's code.

4.3.4 Extensibility

Although the prototype is scoped for read-only data access, it is desirable to have an implementation without losing the generality. This is to ease extending this framework to handle more complex use cases. Thus the overall implementation attempts to follow *The Open/Closed Principle* (section: 4.1.1) such that, objects interact with each other through interfaces, separated from their implementation. This ensures a loose coupling between classes to allow alternate/multiple implementations in future without the need for major changes in the existing code. The framework thus remains open for extensions but closed for modifications.

A possible challenge could be to keep analysis easily configurable, as this directly influences the "Analysis Development Time". The configuration requirements however may have a wide range of use cases based on specific needs of physics groups. Therefore, the current implementation refrains from having any concrete dependencies of configurable objects. Depending on the future use cases, suitable interfaces may be introduced after the prototyping phase.

4.4 Functional Overview

Figure 4.1 shows a functional overview of ATLAS analysis using RDataFrame. As described in section 3.3.1, a typical analysis using RDataFrame involves three basic code blocks. Definition of transforms/decorations, application of cuts/data reduction actions and then the generation of histograms/N-Tuples. The data frame ensures necessary initialization and executes the event-loop. During this execution, for each event, the data frame attempts to access the data through the data source. If the user activates the *ImpliciteMT* feature at the beginning of the analysis, then this

FIGURE 4.1: xAOD DataSource: Functional Overview. Based on [38]

FIGURE 4.2: Tabular representation of a Tree.
Based on RDataFrame: ROOT Reference Documentation [38] and
ATLAS EDM [28]

execution happens concurrently using multiple threads, each one allocated to a subset of the event range. As the representation of event data varies from experiment to experiment, RDataFrame relies on the data source for domain decomposition and actual data access. For the ATLAS analysis, this functionality is provided by xAOD Data Source. Concretely, it performs two basic functions. First, it splits the xAOD dataset into sub-ranges of events, referred as “tasks”. Each such task can be interpreted as an independent unit of work to be executed by a thread. Secondly, it uses the ATLAS event store (section 2.5) functionality to fetch the data from xAOD files.

Given that each event is independent of others, in principle, the parallel processing of multiple tasks as referred above, should have no constraints on data access. Exclusive assignment of each event range to exactly one thread rules out any possibilities of event-level data races, thereby making the concurrent access implicitly thread-safe. However, in general most analyses involve complex data dependencies even within an event. For example, functions using multiple properties across physics objects or transforms/filters using external tools which in-turn may need user-defined parameters beyond the event data. Furthermore, the data may have to pass through chains/graphs of such functional dependencies before it gets ready for final output histogram or N-Tuple. Hence, the access and (re)use of data is trivial only in case of tabular data sets whereby events are represented along rows and

variables along columns. However, the ATLAS EDM relies on a tree structure. The “CollectionTree” of xAOD format uses a hierarchy of nested objects up to arbitrary depth. Resolving such complex dependencies during the event-loop significantly adds computational complexity. This necessitates RDataFrame to know experiment specific details of each supported data format. The RDataSource interface resolves this difficulty by applying the *Dependency Inversion Principle* (section: 4.1.1). This abstraction allows RDataFrame to execute the event-loop without knowing the data structures and facilitates the data source to provide the experiment-specific implementation.

Conceptually, when RDataFrame attempts to read an event, the data source maps its tree structure into a columnar view so that RDataFrame can use it as a table. Figure 4.2 shows an example of this mapping. In this case, the xAOD::EventInfo object is shown as a simple branch of xAOD CollectionTree, with its class members as leaves. Each event contains exactly one EventInfo object which describes that event. The data source maps each class member as a “column” which is then accessed by the data frame using C++ pointers, referred to as “Column Readers”. During event-loop execution, when a particular event is set as the current event, all its data becomes accessible through a “row” of Column Readers, each one pointing to exactly one variable. These variables can be either standalone objects or collections pointing to any of the auxiliary container types described in section 2.6.

Column Readers being pointers, take full advantage of C++ executable objects. These can be instances of arbitrary types including C++ lambda functions, function objects, or pointers to pre-initialized tools. This allows application of user-defined transformations, which may use arbitrary parameters or even (re)use other existing columns as arguments. Thus the overall outcome is a generic mechanism to handle complex event-local dependencies while allowing the data frame to easily iterate over events as if the data had the tabular form. Once the data frame reads required columns, it solves the function call graph (section 3.3) and returns the references of analysis results such as histograms/NTuples back to the analysis code.

FIGURE 4.3: RDataFrame event-loop. Based on ROOT Reference Documentation [38]

4.5 Functional Requirements: As a Data Source

Most of the foundation required for data source is provided by an interface `ROOT::RDataSource` [39] which follows the “Template Method” (section: 4.1.2) pattern to ensure initialization, execution and finalization of event-loop. Arbitrary data sources can implement this interface to be compliant with `RDataFrame`. This guarantees a well-defined execution sequence followed by `RDataFrame` as shown in Figure 4.3. The data source provides an experiment-specific implementation for each step of this sequence. Some of these steps are executed in parallel. For a consistent and easy reference, `RDataFrame` uses an ordered set of integers – “Slot Numbers” as an ordering scheme to dynamically map worker threads to tasks. This facilitates both the data frame and the data source to identify and manage all thread local resources, in terms of slot numbers.

The rest of this section describes these steps and corresponding functional requirements considered for the data source implementation. The names of these steps are exactly the same as the pure virtual function names of `RDataSource` interface. However, the function parameters and return values are omitted here for brevity. The data frame interprets events along rows/entries of a tabular data structure. Thus, in the following, “entry” refers to a particular “event”, and “column” refers to a data variable in the context.

- `SetNSlots`: This function prepares the data source for the required level of parallelism. During this call, the data frame informs the data source about the number of slots that will be used for the parallel execution of the event-loop. The data source can use this information for its initialization and domain decomposition. This is a process invariant for the data source, as the level of parallelism once declared, remains unchanged throughout the analysis.
- `GetColumnReaders`: This function allows the data frame to extract column readers for a particular variable from the data source. As described in the previous section, the data frame interprets each variable as a column of tabular data. For accessing each such column concurrently during the event-loop, it first retrieves a set of `Column Readers` from the data source. For a given variable, each instance of a column reader maps to the thread-local memory

location of that variable. Hence, a critical requirement for the data source is to ensure that all column readers point to the right memory locations during the event-loop.

- **Initialise**: The data frame invokes this function just before the execution of the event-loop. This allows the data source to prepare itself for starting the event-loop such as splitting the dataset into tasks or initialization of any parameters influencing the data access during the event-loop.
- **GetEntryRanges**: The entry ranges are contiguous sub-ranges of events. Each range represents an independent task, later to be allocated to a thread. This allows multiple ranges to be processed simultaneously. The data source may use arbitrary granularity of tasks. However, the sequence of ranges must be contiguous, with no entries skipped. In addition, the entry range should not be returned more than once.
- **InitSlot**: This function informs the data source that a particular thread is about to start processing the data associated with that slot. Thus it is called multiple time concurrently during the event-loop. During this call, the data source is expected to prepare the thread-local instance of input data files and prepare necessary initialization of the ATLAS event store.
- **SetEntry**: This function informs the data source that a certain thread is about to start working on a certain event. This function is called concurrently multiple times during the event-loop. For a given thread it is invoked once per event. During this call, the data source must fetch the data from the ATLAS event store and initialize all column readers. The data frame then uses these column readers to solve the function call graph as described in section 3.3. The initialization of Column Readers is an event-level state invariant. Thus, the Column Readers once initialized, should remain valid until after the data frame is done processing the current event.
- **FinaliseSlot**: This function informs the data source that a certain thread has finished working on a certain range of entries. As a postcondition, the data source must release any task level resources or reset its state that may influence next task.
- **Finalise**: This function informs the data source that the data frame has finished the event-loop execution. The data source must release any loop level resources during this function.

4.6 Functional Requirements: As an Event Store client

The data source is an “Adapter”(section: 4.1.2) between `RDataFrame` and the ATLAS event store. Thus, apart from being a data provider to the data frame, it also acts as a client of the ATLAS event store. An important requirement derives from the objective of extensibility as discussed in section 4.3.4. The EDM interfaces ensure extensibility via their separation (section 2.5) from concrete auxiliary storage. In order to correctly benefit from this feature, it implies that all clients of ATLAS event store must access the data only through interface containers. The data source, therefore, should not explicitly hold any concrete instances of auxiliary containers.

FIGURE 4.4: xAOD DataSource: Class Diagram

The second requirement derives from the physics application. Specifically, for the `SetEntry` step, a code contract to be followed with the event store is that the data source must not assume any state or hold any data across the events. The acquisition and release of the event local resources must follow the fact that each physics event is independent of others. In addition, resource ownership also applies within the scope of the task as well as the event-loop. Thus, the resources acquired during `InitSlot` must be released during `FinaliseSlot` and those acquired during `Initialise` must be released during `Finalise`.

4.7 Overview of the Data Source Architecture

As shown in figure 4.4, the data source package consists of three classes. This section outlines their ownership and high-level interactions among them followed by a detailed description of the execution sequence.

- `TxAODdataSource`: This is the primary class of the data source package. It provides experiment specific implementation for the `ROOT::RDataSource` interface, to fulfill all functional requirements (section: 4.5) as a data source. The data frame invokes the event-loop sequence through this interface. From the data frame’s perspective, this class is also the primary interface for data access during the event-loop. However, for modularity (section: 4.3.3), it delegates this responsibility to a collaborator class – `TEventCursor`.
- `TEventCursor`: This class provides the groundwork necessary for the parallel connection between the data frame and the ATLAS event store. Concretely, it owns a thread-local instance of event store – `TEvent` and a set of data handles. Analogous to a cursor, it positions itself to a particular event to be processed by a slot. It sets the event store to point to the requested event and then updates all data handles. This process repeats, as the data frame steps through all events. This sequence limits the scope of data access strictly to one event at a time, as expected by functional requirements (section: 4.6). In this context, the “update” of data handle refers to the actual retrieval of data from event store and the initialization of column readers. For modularity (section: 4.3.3), `TEventCursor` delegates this this functionality to another helper class –

FIGURE 4.5: The Data Handle

`THandle`.

The data source maintains a one-to-one mapping of event cursors and slots. Thus, each event cursor exclusively remains associated with its slot throughout the event-loop. This association guarantees the thread-local consistency, as expected by the data frame.

- `THandle`: This class implements the concept of a “column handle”. In principle, this can be any arbitrary functional object that the data frame can use as a column. However, the current implementation supports it as a read-only data handle. This class encapsulates the pointer-to-pointer-to-pointer relationship as shown in figure 4.5. Concretely, it connects a memory address of a data variable, to a `Column Reader` via a constant pointer. This configuration allows the data source to dynamically update the memory address of a variable as it steps through events. The data frame thus gets seamless access to the memory address via the `Column Reader`. The middle pointer, being constant, ensures this linkage throughout the event-loop by protecting it against any surprising effects due to accidental modifications.

4.8 Analysis Execution Sequence

In the following, a general analysis example describes the interaction between above-referred objects. The overall analysis execution sequence has two broad steps, initialization and event-loop. For ease of technical reference, this section separates initialization into two theoretical substeps, namely “data source initialization”, and the “event-loop initialization”.

4.8.1 DataSource Initialization

Figure 4.6 shows the data source initialization sequence. The analysis code activates implicit parallelism using `ROOT`’s interface function `EnableImplicitMT`. Then, the factory function `make_xAODdataFrame` uses the path of input data set to configure an instance of `TxAODdataSource`. The data source constructor first reads metadata from the `xAOD` format. For this, it first creates a `TChain` object and associates it with a new instance of `TEvent`. It then reads the `EventFormat` branch of `xAOD CollectionTree` and populates a map of all available branch names with

FIGURE 4.6: DataSource Initialization Sequence

FIGURE 4.7: xAOD DataSource: Event-Loop Sequence.
Based on RDataFrame: ROOT Reference Documentation [38]

their corresponding class names. This mapping is later used to lookup C++ type name, for a given branch/variable name requested by the analysis code. The function `make_xAODdataFrame` then associates the data source with a new instance of `RDataFrame` and returns its reference to analysis code for further usage.

4.8.2 Event Loop

After the initialization, the analysis code uses the data frame's interface for analysis features such as column definitions, decorations, event filters and generates analysis results such as histograms/NTuples. As discussed in section 3.3.2, all `RDataFrame` analysis results are proxy objects characterized by lazy initialization. Thus, the event-loop triggers after the first access to a result. Figure 4.7 shows this execution sequence. The data frame initializes event-loop with `SetNSlots` to notify the data source about the number of slots planned for parallelism. The data source creates a set of `TEventCursors`, one per slot. The data frame then invokes `Initialise` to allow data source to split event range into tasks. It then collects these tasks through `GetEntryRanges` and schedules them for concurrent execution. Each task refers to event-loop execution on a sub-range, between `InitSlot` and `FinaliseSlot`. For each slot, the data source creates a thread-local instance of `TEvent` and uses it to

initialise corresponding `TEventCursor`. Note that, both the `TEventCursor` and `TEvent` are initialized only once per slot, and destructed after completion of the last task of the slot. This reuse of `TEventCursor` for multiple tasks on a given slot is completely safe as none of these objects rely on any state or information beyond the scope of the individual event. After completion of all tasks, the data frame invokes `Finalise` to allow the data source to clean up its resources.

4.8.3 Data Access

This section takes a closer look at the data access sequence. Figure 4.8 shows a detailed view of a task execution with an example of access to one data variable. The data frame prepares itself by invoking `GetColumnReaders`. It uses the column name to query these readers. The data source forwards this query to event cursors on all slots. Each event cursor then creates an instance of `THandle` and returns its column reader. The event cursor creates the handle on its first use and then caches it into a set for its reuse throughout the event-loop. The data source returns column readers strictly ordered by their slot indices.

During the event-loop, the data frame dynamically schedules multiple tasks for concurrent processing. For each task, it invokes `SetEntry` once per event. Thus, for a given slot, the data source delegates this request to the event cursor, which in turn, invokes `getEntry` on `TEvent`. Consequently, this sets the requested event “active” and ready for data access. The event cursor then calls `update` on all its handles. Each handle then uses the `retrieve` function on `TEvent`, thereby initializing the data address. The data frame then reads these addresses through the column readers and executes the function call graph.

FIGURE 4-8: xAOD DataSource: Data Access Sequence.
Based on RDataFrame: ROOT Reference Documentation [38]

4.9 Implementation

This section remarks some motivations that steered the structural and functional features of the implementation. In particular, it describes the low-level requirements and implementation choices considered to address the design objectives listed in section 4.3. Rest of this section revisits those objectives from the implementation perspective.

4.9.1 Scalability

Following the Amdahl's Law [64], the key to maximize scalability is to attempt reducing the serial component of the parallel code. The most common source of such serial fraction is the suboptimal concurrency usually resulting from I/O waits and explicit synchronizations. `RDataFrame` addresses this difficulty with the thread-local execution of event-loop. Each thread owns its task, thereby eliminating the need for explicit synchronization across the tasks. The data source follows this pattern by using thread-local instances of `TEventCursor`, `THandle` and `TEvent` to avoid synchronization overheads. However, this is considered as trade-off to compromise memory for CPU time. For N slots, the cost of space for these objects is $O(N)$. With N sufficiently small, the cost in space is justifiable given the benefits of parallelism. However, the growth coefficient may vary for `THandle`, based on the complexity of analysis. Nevertheless, the number of handles is assumed to be relatively small based on two considerations. First, the construction of handles is need-based. The data frame requests `Column Readers` only for those variables accessed by analysis code, at the most once per variable. Secondly, the event cursor reuses its handles for all tasks scheduled on its slot. The support for such reuse without side effects is the motivation for implementing the `THandle` as a stateless object.

The current implementation has two sources of the serial fraction. The first one is an explicit read lock for file access by the factory function `makeDataChain`. This is essential for thread-safety as multiple event cursors may concurrently attempt to read the same data set from disk. The profiling results (section: 5.6.4) show that this does not have any noticeable impact on scalability. The second source of the serial fraction is the initialization sequence. This is observed to be significant on relatively short duration analyses and is currently left as an open task for future work.

Apart from synchronization overheads, the effectiveness of available parallelism significantly depends upon the granularity of concurrent tasks. As the initial implementation, the granularity of tasks was set by uniform task distribution, thereby equally splitting the event data to available slots. Based on performance testing and profiling observations, this was optimized in the later version of the data source. See chapter 5 for details of performance testing and optimization.

4.9.2 Minimal Abstraction Overhead

The choice of design patterns and data structures significantly influences the abstraction overheads introduced by framework layers. Depending on the complexity of use cases, the impact on the end-to-end cost of analysis may vary, both in space and time.

Considering spatial cost, the usual sources of such overheads include temporary objects, transient copies, and objects with superfluous states and life-spans. A preferred solution to such issues is minimalism in combination with the C++ idiom, *Resource Acquisition Is Initialization* [48] (RAII). It follows the common approach for all resources, “Constructor allocates, Destructor cleans”. This sequence ensures the optimum resource management even under exceptional/fatal conditions, as the C++ guarantees calling destructors of all scoped objects through stack unwinding. The data source implementation throughout uses this pattern. Furthermore, the data source extensively uses C++ smart pointers [35]. In particular, all cases of passing an object by reference are handled by `std::unique_ptr`. Performance wise, unique pointers are equivalent to conventional pointers, but they offer some functional benefits. Their declaration itself indicates that the pointer takes the ownership of the memory. Thus, when such a pointer goes out of scope, the destructor of the referred object is automatically called. Thus, the caller need not be concerned about its clean-up, even under exceptional conditions.

A particular example of the above-referred concept is the initialization of `TEvent`. For a given slot, at the beginning of the first task, the data source creates an instance of `TChain` and passes its ownership to `TEvent`. The event store then owns the chain until it completes all tasks of that slot. The data source does not need to keep track of which chains are to be destructed on which slots. This is because, the unique pointers holding `TEvent` references, automatically call their destructors when they are reset after completion of the last task. Consequently, each `TEvent` destructor takes care of releasing its data chain.

Considering temporal cost, the implementation choice for the life-span of `THandle` and `TEventCursor` objects is based on two assumptions. First, for the effective use of available parallelism, the data source strives for fine granularity. Thus, for the usual and worst-case scenario, it holds the condition ($nTasks \gg nSlots$). Secondly, the number of tasks are assumed to grow with the size of data. Therefore, the life-span of handles and event cursors is set to be slot-local rather than task-local to minimize the frequency of construction and destruction of these objects. On the other hand, this introduces a relatively much smaller penalty of bookkeeping, as the data source needs to know the completion point of the last task on each slot to release these objects.

4.9.3 Modularity:

For functional modularity, the data source splits the overall functionality into a hierarchy of functional units. Each unit represents one class interface to address a coherent subset of requirements. Concretely, the class `TxAODdataSource` is an Adapter (section: 4.1.2), between `RDataFrame` and `TEvent`. It splits this dual-responsibility into two separate requirements. First, It provides implementation of `RDataSource` interface to support the interaction with `RDataFrame`. Secondly, it delegates the interaction with `TEvent` to `TEventCursor`. This allows, both the data source and event cursor implementations to evolve independently and adapt any external changes in future versions of `RDataFrame` and `TEvent`.

Another example functional separation is between `TEventCursor` and `THandle`. In this case, the event cursor provides the necessary implementation for creation, lookup, and update of all its handles, but delegates any data access calls to corresponding

handles. This separation allows, both the event cursor and the handle to evolve independently and leaves the handle free to implement alternative methods of data access.

The data source also ensures structural modularity through the composition of objects. In this context, the composition refers to a structural hierarchy. The complex objects are built using smaller and simpler objects, each supporting a small subset of functionality. To this end, the top level class `TxAODdataSource` has the longest life-span. It is composed of multiple `TEventCursors`, each having a slot-local life-span. Similarly, `TEventCursor` is composed of multiple `THandles`.

4.9.4 Extensibility:

As described in section 4.3.4, it's given that the data source is expected to support more complex use cases after the prototyping phase. Various methods of accessing xAOD data (section 2.6) would steer these use cases. Thus, the most likely influenced class by these future requirements is `THandle`. Therefore, its implementation is separated from its interface. Concretely, the ability to access the data from event store is abstracted into a pure virtual interface – `IHandle`. The `THandle` implements this interface for a read-only data handle. As the event cursor has no knowledge of the concrete type of handles, it remains loosely coupled with the event store. Supporting more methods of data access needs additional implementations of `IHandle` without the need for changing the existing framework. As a remark, the handle concept can be extended to read-write data handle or even a tool handle to represent a “function column” of a tabular data set.

4.10 Verification and Validation

This section documents the process followed for testing the prototype. In this context, the verification refers to checking the code contracts and responding appropriately through error/exception handling mechanism. The validation refers to ensuring that the results of the analysis are as expected.

4.10.1 Error/Exception Handling

As discussed in section 4.9.2, all classes follow RAII for resource management. This configuration inherently reduces the probability of resource leaks. However, in practice, the run-time errors are inevitable. The data source follows the same exception handling pattern as that of `RDataFrame`. Concretely, all public functions check their necessary pre-conditions before the beginning of the execution. If any of the code contracts is broken, then a run-time exception is thrown with a brief description of the error. The public functions catch any other runtime exceptions originated from other parts of data source, and re-throw them. This explicitly highlights that the exception is from the data source, indicating the public function as its origin. This helps to narrow down the debug steps, while the low-level details remain available for further analysis of error.

In general, the location of exception handling or recovery is almost always different than the origin of the error. The framework code does not have prior knowledge to recover from exceptional conditions safely. Thus it is up to the user to choose suitable recovery options when possible. The objects throwing exceptions are however

expected to leave the program in a “valid state”. To be precise about the valid state, the C++ standard defines *Exception Guarantees* [47] into three categories as outlined below.

- **Basic Guarantee:** The classes supporting basic guarantee ensure that all class invariants are maintained all the time, and no resources are leaked. As discussed in section 4.9.2, all objects of data source provide this guarantee for memory through their usage of smart pointers and RAII implementation. This concept applies to mutex locks as well. The data source uses scoped locks for all instances. If an exception is thrown while the lock is acquired, the destructor of lock guarantees its release once it goes out of scope.
- **Strong Guarantee:** This is a bit stronger requirement in addition to basic guarantee. For key operations, this implies that either the operation succeeds or it has no effect. The `TEventCursor` provides this guarantee for caching the handles. It maintains the collection of handles as a set to prevent replication of handles. Hence, for a given variable name, there exists a unique handle throughout the event-loop. Thus, in case of failure of creating or inserting a new handle, the event cursor catches the exception and aborts the operation. As the underlying STL set also maintains the strong guarantee, the whole sequence ensures that the original set remains unaltered.
- **No-throw Guarantee:** This is an even stronger code contract, hence usually supported by a few simple operations. The No-Throw Guarantee implies that, in addition to the basic guarantee, the operation will not throw an exception. The only object supporting this guarantee is `THandle`. This is to fulfill the requirement by STL containers, where the objects using move semantics are expected to provide No-Throw guarantee for their move constructors and move assignment operators. This allows STL containers to provide the strong guarantee when an object is moved into a container.

4.10.2 Integration Testing

For validation of prototype, end-to-end integration tests are defined using simple analysis building blocks. These include three basic representative use cases as below:

- **Read Standalone Objects:** This category validates that the data source can successfully read standalone leaves of `CollectionTree` from an xAOD dataset and perform basic analysis operations using `RDataFrame`.
- **Read Container Objects:** This category validates that the data source can successfully read data vectors from auxiliary containers and perform basic analysis operations using `RDataFrame`.
- **Apply Event Filter:** This category validates event filter functionality on both standalone and auxiliary container objects with a bit more analysis operations using `RDataFrame`.

For all the above-referred categories, the baseline tests were first implemented using `AnaAlgorithm Framework` [1] for the creation of some histograms. Corresponding integration tests were then implemented using `RDataFrame`. The resulting histograms were then compared with baseline results. Table 4.1 documents all integration tests based on `RDataFrame`.

	Integration Test Name	Execution Sequence
1	ReadEventInfo	Create RDataFrame instance Read EventInfo object Evaluate min, max of EventInfo.eventNumber Create histogram of EventInfo.runNumber Validate results
2	ReadSingleVectorContainer	Create RDataFrame instance Read Electrons container Evaluate min, max of Electron.pt Validate results
3	Histo1D	Create RDataFrame instance Read Electrons container Create histogram of Electron.pt Validate results
4	FilterMinMax	Create RDataFrame instance Read Electrons container Apply cut: $\text{Electron.pt} \geq \text{ptThreshold}$ Filter events: $\text{ptCutVector.size} \geq \text{nElectorns}$ Evaluate min, max of pt on filtered events Validate results

TABLE 4.1: Integration Tests

4.10.3 Unit Testing

Unit testing [68] aims to detect the broken code early and often as it evolves. This objective motivates the splitting of implementation targets into tiny slices of functionality, each implemented and tested as an independent unit. Thus, each failing unit test represents an unfulfilled functional requirement. Once the sufficient implementation is done to make such test pass, all other existing unit tests are re-run. At this point, the state of all passing unit tests validates that the new functionality has been added without any side effects.

This prototype uses Google Test [20] framework for unit testing. Throughout the implementation, the *Test Driven Design* [67](TDD) approach is followed. The failing unit tests are written first, to declare functional requirements of a unit. Then the necessary implementation is added to address those requirements. As a general observation, if a newly added implementation passes its driving unit test, but fails any of the other unit tests; its an indicator of a possible design flaw, especially the presence of tight coupling. Often a closer look at the failing unit tests provides clues about refined design solutions. With the addition of more unit tests, interleaved with incremental implementation, the design gets driven by the tests. In addition to the Google Test framework, the Valgrind [63], tool is used to re-run all these unit tests to locate memory leaks. This validates the basic guarantee as described in section 4.10.1. Appendix A documents all unit tests currently used by DataSource.

Chapter 5

Performance Testing and Optimization

The last chapter concluded with the validation of basic functionality, correctness, and stability of current implementation. Observing that the prototype works correctly, the focus of this chapter shifts to the validation of performance objectives (section 4.3) in particular, the scalability and minimal abstraction overhead. The chapter first documents the instrumentation efforts and the environment setup for performance testing. It then reports the preliminary results of performance testing and profiling observations, followed by the documentation of an optimization attempt. The chapter concludes with the results of re-testing and profiling of the optimized version.

5.1 Instrumentation and Test Setup

For the preliminary performance measurements, three analysis applications were implemented using the same use cases applied during the integration testing as listed in section 4.10.2. All performance testing is done using compiled C++ applications within a lab environment. i.e. a stand-alone desktop using minimal background services and assuming that all resources are available for the current user. The preliminary observations are based on wall time measurements. For the later analysis, all measurements were done using wall time, initialization time and event-loop execution time. In this context, the initialization time refers to the duration between the start of program execution and the end of the function `TxAODDataSource::Initialize`. The foundation required for these measurements is implemented at two levels. First, the instrumentation support within `DataSource` and the second, a python implementation to collect a statistical summary of measurements from multiple test runs.

5.1.1 DataSource Instrumentation

The instrumentation within the `DataSource` is implemented in a utility class named `TLapTimer`. A test application can be configured from the command line to associate this class with `DataSource`. The data source uses it to record the time-lapse data. The location of this data collection can be anywhere within the data source code. The test application logs this data into a text file at the end of program execution.

For logging and command line interpretation, two more utility classes are provided, namely `TLogFile` and `TOptions`. Both classes are implemented in a separate package named `AppUtils`. The `TOptions` class provides the implementation for parsing test parameters from the command line arguments. These parameters include the number of threads, a flag to enable/disable `ImplicitMT` feature, paths to input data files, and the name of output log file. Using this setup, the current implementation of `DataSource` logs the wall time, initialization time and event-loop execution time.

5.1.2 Python Test Scripts

The python implementation includes the main test script `PerfTest.py` and a helper class named `TestCase`. The main script parses command line arguments, configures a new instance of `TestCase` and executes it. The `TestCase` class encapsulates the execution of a C++ application. Given the executable name and its command line arguments, `TestCase` runs it for a specified number of iterations. After this execution, it reads all the above-referred metrics from the log file and writes out the statistical mean and standard deviation values for each metric.

The `TestCase` class is exception aware. In the event of an abrupt termination, it logs the exception details and skips that entry from the data used for the statistical summary. This is implemented to prevent any statistical outliers due to exceptional test failures. However, `TestCase` captures this failure rate by logging the number of successful iterations in the summary. Throughout the testing of this prototype, this metric and the standard deviation values are used for a sanity check to ensure the application stability before using the data for further analysis.

The `TestCase` follows a three step execution sequence: `initialize`, `execute` and `finalize`. This facilitates two modes of execution, namely `CacheMode.Warm` and `CacheMode.Cold`. During the warm cache mode, the `initialize` function invokes an extra warm-up iteration and skips it from the data used for computing the statistical summary. During the cold cache mode, the `initialize` function invokes a system call to clear the cache before each iteration.

Putting all the above-referred features together, the overall test execution can be described as follows. The main test script `PerfTest.py` accepts the test application name, command line arguments, and test parameters. It then configures an instance of `TestCase` and executes it. The `TestCase` runs the application for the specified number of iterations using the specified cache mode. During each iteration, the `DataSource` logs the time-lapse data as columns of metrics. After completion of all iterations, the `TestCase` reads the log file and writes out a statistical summary of all columns in a separate output file.

5.1.3 Test Setup

	DataSource[0.1.02] Test Environment
Hardware	Intel i7 Quad-Core CPU @3.6 GHz, 8GB RAM Hyper-Threading Disabled
OS	Ubuntu 16.04.LTS
ROOT	6.13/02
AnalysisBase	21.2.31
xAODdataSource	0.1.02
Dataset	data17_13TeV.00328263.physics_Main... deriv.DAOD_HIGG2D2.f836_m1824_p3213 Set of 50 compressed DxAOD files Total Size ~25GB

TABLE 5.1: DataSource[0.1.02] Test Environment

This section describes the test setup of the initial implementation referred to as the DataSource[0.1.02]. Table 5.1 documents the test execution environment used for these tests. The corresponding analysis use cases are described below:

- **ReadAuxElement:**
Reads one stand-alone xAOD object – xAOD::EventInfo,
Defines two columns EventInfo.eventNumber and EventInfo.runNumber,
Computes Min,Max of EventInfo.eventNumber,
Generates a histogram of EventInfo.runNumber
- **Histo1D:**
Reads one xAOD vector container – xAOD::Electrons,
Defines a new column Electron.pt,
Generates a histogram of Electron.pt
- **FilterMinMax:**
Reads one xAOD vector container – xAOD::Electrons,
Applies a cut (Electron.pt > ptThreshold) to derive a new column ptCut,
Applies an event filter (ptCutVector.size > 2),
Computes Min,Max of ptCut column on filtered events

5.2 Preliminary Results: Version[0.1.02]

In order to observe the influence of hardware, all tests were first executed in the warm cache mode using a spinning disk drive (HDD) and a solid state drive (SSD). Both of these test sets were then repeated using the cold cache mode. This section documents the wall time and speedup observations obtained from this exercise and concludes with the interpretation of these results.

As a general remark, all performance plots are based on the statistical mean of time measurements obtained from 20 iterations. Furthermore, the observations from sequential execution are labeled as NoMT. In this context, the term “sequential execution” refers to a test run without using the ImplicitMT feature of RDataFrame. Section 3.3.2 describes the usage of ImplicitMT in an analysis. The time measurements

obtained from the sequential execution are used as the baseline reference for computing speedup, which is defined as below:

$$\text{Speedup } S(t) := \frac{W_{\text{NoMT}}}{W(t)_{\text{ImplicitMT}}}$$

where, t = Number of active threads

W_{NoMT} = Wall time of sequential execution

$W(t)_{\text{ImplicitMT}}$ = Wall time of parallel execution

The special case ($t = 1$) refers to single-threaded execution with the `ImplicitMT` feature enabled. Although this case does not reflect a practical analysis usage, it is executed for observing the overhead of `ImplicitMT` with respect to the sequential execution.

5.2.1 Interpretation of Preliminary Results

Figure 5.1 shows wall time and speedup plots obtained from the above-referred test runs. The relevant observations are outlined below:

1. Referring to figure 5.1, all sub-plots at ($t = 1$) indicate the initialization cost of implicit parallelism. However, for all these cases the relative increase in wall time with respect to the sequential execution is less than 2.5%. Thus, during the initial performance study, this overhead is assumed to contribute marginally in the total overhead. However, this interpretation is subject to the condition that the initialization cost does not grow with the number of threads. This factor is inconclusive based on these observations. Therefore, the subsequent tests were executed with wall time, initialization time, and event-loop time separately logged from the `DataSource`.
2. Considering the warm cache mode, the observations on SSD (figure 5.1(A,B)) and HDD (figure 5.1(C,D)) both show the similar results. This observation shows that if the disk latency is factored out, then the scalability of this implementation is unaffected by any other hardware-specific factors. In both cases the speedup plots are non-linear and they converge at ~ 1.3 . The non-linearity implies that the serial fraction of the code is increasing with the number of threads. Considering the worst case of ($t = 4$), the observed speedup is $\sim 32\%$ of the ideal speedup. This observation indicates a sub-optimal utilization of resources and hints about the existence of possible performance bottlenecks. Section: 5.4 describes these bottlenecks revealed after a performance profiling exercise.
3. Referring to figure 5.1(A) and (C) the wall time plots for all three test cases show a consistent time offset between them. The test case of reading stand-alone objects `ReadAuxElement` takes ~ 0.5 seconds more than the vector container test `Histo1D`. This constant offset irrespective of the number of threads hints that the difference is likely due to the duration of first access to `xADD::EventInfo` versus that to the `xADD::Electrons` container. A possible reason is interpreted as: for all multi-threaded executions ($t > 1$), once the data is fetched from the memory into the processor cache by the first accessing thread, it becomes readily available for other threads at no additional cost.
4. Considering the cold cache mode, some additional I/O overhead is anticipated due to the effect of disk latency during each iteration. Comparing the case of

(A) SSD, Warm Cache: Wall Time

(B) SSD, Warm Cache: Speedup With respect to Sequential Execution

(C) HDD, Warm Cache: Wall Time

(D) HDD, Warm Cache: Speedup With respect to Sequential Execution

(E) SSD, Cold Cache: Wall Time

(F) SSD, Cold Cache: Speedup With respect to Sequential Execution

(G) HDD, Cold Cache: Wall Time

(H) HDD, Cold Cache: Speedup With respect to Sequential Execution

FIGURE 5.1: DataSource [0.1.02] Preliminary Performance Observations

SSD cold cache (figure 5.1(E)) with both the warm cache cases (figures 5.1(A, C)), the last observation of vector container performing better is reproduced only by cases ($t > 1$). A possible reason for this is interpreted as: for a given iteration, the disk latency is experienced only by the first accessing thread. Thus, the subsequent access by other threads still benefits from the cache locality. However, for ($t = 1$ and NoMT), it appears that the cost of fetching a vector container from the memory into the processor cache outweighs the above-referred time offset during its first access. Figure 5.1(F) shows that the disk latency also appears to impact the speedup. In this case, the speedup converges to ~ 1.1 . Considering the worst case of ($t = 4$) the observed speedup is $\sim 28\%$ of the ideal speedup.

5. Referring to HDD cold cache mode (figure 5.1(G)), the effect of disk latency has increased the wall time of vector container tests by ~ 11 times compared to those of HDD warm cache mode (figure 5.1(C)). A constant wall time offset of ~ 37 seconds is observed between the tests of vector containers and `ReadAuxElement`. Furthermore, for cases ($t > 1$) the saturation of speedup at ~ 0.8 indicates an I/O bound situation where the disk latency has completely constrained the scalability.

Referring to item 2 above, the warm cache mode validates that the scalability of implementation is independent of hardware, provided that the disk latency is factored out. However, the speedup observations highlight the requirement of a detailed performance study to identify bottlenecks. From items 4 and 5 above, the cold cache mode and the latency of HDD appear to introduce a bias on the performance measurements. In order to eliminate these effects on the testing of the first implementation, the rest of the testing and profiling was done using SSD in the warm cache mode. The re-validation of these tests on alternate hardware is left as an open task for the future work.

5.3 Intel VTune Amplifier

The Intel VTune Amplifier [27] (VTune), was used for performance analysis during this prototyping phase. This section briefly describes some of its relevant definitions, followed by a brief overview of performance metrics referred throughout this chapter.

5.3.1 Hot-Spot Analysis

Hot-spot analysis [26] is used to understand the overall CPU utilization by various components of the application and to locate expensive sections of code referred to as hot-spots. To benefit the most from the optimization process, such sections are analyzed first to identify and fix the most influencing performance bottlenecks. However, some hot-spots may perform useful work, in such cases, the next significant hot-spot is analyzed. The process is repeated until all known bottlenecks are fixed. For hot-spot analysis, VTune uses two sampling-based collection modes as outlined below:

- **User-mode sampling [62]:** In this mode, a data collector profiles the application using the operating system's timer. It collects the data only from the application under test. It periodically interrupts the running process at a pre-defined interval. After each interval, it collects samples of all active instruction

addresses and captures function call stacks for each sample. This mode is optimized for identification of algorithm level bottlenecks such as synchronization overheads and sub-optimal CPU utilization.

- **Hardware event-based sampling [24]:** VTune uses this mode for a system-wide data collection. This simultaneously profiles all processes running on the system using the hardware events observed by Performance Measurement Units (PMU) on the CPU. Unlike user-mode sampling, this method captures only statistically important samples which are triggered by PMUs above a pre-defined threshold. Therefore, this method has a relatively smaller profiling overhead compared to the user-mode sampling. However, due to statistical nature, it needs a sufficiently large number of samples for reliable measurements. The performance data captured by this method is optimized to locate micro-architectural bottlenecks such as sub-optimal utilization of vector processing capabilities and effects of first level cache misses.

The purpose of this profiling exercise was to identify the bottlenecks within the event-loop execution. Hence, the user-mode sampling collection was used for all profiling test runs with the focus on algorithm level observations.

5.3.2 Threading Analysis

Threading analysis [59] helps to understand the overall concurrent behavior of the application. It provides tools to measure available parallelism and to locate sources causing inefficient use of available cores. These sources may include thread contention, under/over-subscription of threads and explicitly blocking parts of the code such as synchronization locks or I/O waits. A threading analysis workflow involves execution of a parallel application within the VTune's environment. During this execution, VTune periodically collects snapshots of the information relevant to the utilization of all available cores.

5.3.3 Performance Metrics

The profiling data referred above includes vast information collected from several parts of the system. VTune categorizes this information into Performance Metrics relevant for each type of analysis. This section follows Intel VTune documentation [27] to describe some of these metrics used through the rest of this chapter.

- **Elapsed Time:** The wall time measured from the beginning to the end of data collection.
- **CPU Time:** The time during which the CPU is actively executing the application.
- **Spin Time:** This is the wait time during which, the CPU is busy. In this context, the term "wait" refers to a thread logically waiting to perform useful work, while CPU is busy spinning. Depending upon the application design, some spin time may be preferable if it prevents thread context-switching overheads. However, too much spin time hints about a possible loss of parallelism. Thus, one of the objectives of threading analysis is to identify unexpected locations in the timeline showing excessive spin time and then reconsider the synchronization strategy for optimization.

- **Overhead Time:** This is the fraction of CPU Time spent on overhead due to synchronization of known threading libraries. (e.g. system synchronization calls, Intel TBB) Although such calls are beyond the control of application under test, this metric helps to identify call stacks using expensive system calls. The origin and frequency of such call stacks provide insight into the roots of these overheads.
- **Effective CPU Time:** This is the fraction of CPU Time spent in the user code. This excludes Spin Time and Overhead Time. Its an indicator of the effective use of a given CPU core.
- **Average Effective CPU Utilization:** This metric shows average CPU utilization by excluding the Spin and Overhead time. The ideal value of this metric is equal to the number of logical CPU cores.
- **Simultaneously Utilized Logical CPUs** This metric indicates the degree of CPU utilization over the elapsed time. A 100% CPU utilization means that the application keeps all the logical CPU cores busy during the entire elapsed time. By default, VTune classifies this metric into four ranges as below:
 - **Idle:** The total CPU Time on all threads is less than 0.5% of available CPU Time on one core.
 - **Poor:** The number of simultaneously running CPUs is less than or equal to 50% of the target CPU utilization.
 - **OK:** The number of simultaneously running CPUs is between 51-85% of the target CPU utilization.
 - **Ideal:** The number of simultaneously running CPUs is between 86-100% of the target CPU utilization.
- **Wait Time:** This is the time spent by a thread waiting for blocking function calls or the synchronization. This metric is reported per-thread. Therefore, the total wait time may exceed the elapsed time of the execution.
- **Wait Count:** This indicates the number of times a thread had to wait due to blocking function calls or the synchronization. This metric along with the Wait Time provides insight into the granularity of a synchronization. A high Wait Count is an indicator of an overused synchronization resource or unsuitable synchronization strategy.
- **Cycles Per Instruction Retired(CPI):** This metric indicates an average approximate duration of a CPU instruction in terms of CPU cycles. For a processor issuing four instructions per cycle, this metric implies a theoretically best $CPI = 0.25$. The ideal CPI refers to a situation such that all instructions issued by the processor are successfully retired.

As a remark, the CPI may be affected by hardware specifics. For example, with Hyper-Threading [12] enabled, two logical threads share the resources of a single physical core. In such case, the ideal CPI becomes 0.5 even though the processor is capable of issuing four instructions per cycle. In order to eliminate any bias of this effect, Hyper-Threading was disabled throughout all the performance profiling exercises.

	DataSource[0.1.02] Profiling Environment
Hardware	Intel i7 Quad-Core CPU @3.6 GHz, 8GB RAM Hyper-Threading Disabled
OS	Ubuntu 16.04.LTS
ROOT	6.13/02
AnalysisBase	21.2.31
xAODdataSource	0.1.02
Dataset	data17_13TeV.00328263.physics_Main... deriv.DAOD_HIGG2D2.f836_m1824_p3213 Set of 50 compressed DxAOD files Total Size ~25GB

TABLE 5.2: DataSource[0.1.02] Profiling Environment

FIGURE 5.2: DataSource[0.1.02] Elapsed Time and Top Hot-Spots

5.4 Performance Analysis

This section documents the performance profiling observations on DataSource[0.1.02]. It begins with the description of a test setup modified for performance profiling, followed by the observations from hot-spot and threading analysis. It then concludes with the interpretations of these observations.

5.4.1 Performance Test Setup

In order to run the analysis little longer during profiling sessions, the Histo1D test case was modified to read some more data per event. The revised test case is described as below:

- Histo1D.MultipleContainers:**
 Reads three xAOD vector containers as listed below:
 xAOD::Electrons, xAOD::Muons and xAOD::Photons,
 Defines 12 columns, one each for data member of xAOD::IParticle interface,
 Generates total 36 histograms, 12 for each vector container.

The rest of this section documents the profiling observations made from the execution of the above-referred test using four threads. Table 5.2, documents the test execution environment. As a general process throughout this prototype, all profiling tests were executed five times. Out of those results, the one with the median value of elapsed time was chosen for further analysis.

5.4.2 Hot-Spot Observations

Figure 5.2 shows a summary of elapsed time and top hot-spots. The elapsed time view further shows a split-up of the CPU time into Effective Time, Spin Time and

FIGURE 5.3: DataSource [0.1.02] Critical Call Stack

Overhead Time. Referring to the theoretically 100% CPU utilization with four available cores, the maximum CPU time would be four times that of the Elapsed Time. This reference maps the maximum CPU Time to 112 seconds for this particular execution. This observation indicates that the actual CPU utilization is only $\sim 32\%$ of its theoretical maximum value. Furthermore, the split-up of CPU Time shows that $\sim 14\%$ of CPU time goes into spinning, while the CPU is busy but threads are waiting. Also, the near-zero value of Overhead Time indicates that the underutilization of CPU is not much contributed by the threading framework calls.

The top hot-spots view lists the most active function calls sorted by their usage of CPU Time. The most expensive CPU user is a system call [vmlinux], which consumes about 17% of the total CPU time. Figure 5.3 shows a bottom-up view of this usage in a tree representation. In this context, each leaf node represents the function originating a call stack ending at the root node. This particular tree shows four different functions, each invoking the function `TBranchElement::GetEntry`. This function is the origin of a common call stack using the top hot-spot [vmlinux]. For each level of this call stack, the CPU Time, CPI Rate, Wait Time, and Instructions Retired are reported. For each function, these metrics are referred to as the sum of the self-utilization and that by all its callers.

For ease of reference, figure 5.3 is remarked by splitting the entire call stack into three separate zones. The CPU Time and Wait Rate metrics indicate that the largest fraction of the CPU Time is spent waiting during the top-most zone used by [vmlinux]. This zone also indicates that the largest number of CPU instructions are executed during this execution compared to its immediate caller `futex_wake`. This observation identifies the top-most zone to be the most expensive part of this call stack. However, referring to the CPI Rate column, the middle zone consumes ~ 7 times higher CPI compared to the ideal CPI of 0.25. This indicates that the middle zone is the most inefficient part, hence a possible bottleneck. The lower-most zone also has a relatively high CPI Rate. However, observing the Instructions Retired metric, this zone affects only $\sim 3\%$ of total CPU instructions executed by the entire call stack. Therefore, the middle zone is considered for a closer look.

Referring to the call stack, this zone starts with a synchronization point at `ROOT::TReentrantRWLock`. This is a read-write mutex lock of re-entrant type. In general, a simple mutex lock cannot be reused to acquire the same resource twice before releasing it. This constraint limits the usage of mutex locks to non-recursive functions. The re-entrant lock resolves this difficulty for recursive functions. The recursive nature of `TBranchElement::GetEntry` function necessitates this type for thread-safe access to the basket buffer data. This data access, in turn, invokes an unlock sequence, causing a system level wait indicated by the top-most zone. The next section describes the observations of concurrency analysis relevant to the middle zone.

5.4.3 Concurrency Observations

Figure 5.4 shows the histograms of effective CPU utilization and thread concurrency. The CPU utilization histogram has the mean close to 0.2, which is referred to as Average Effective CPU Utilization. This observation reproduces the CPU under-utilization as observed earlier during the hot-spot analysis. The peak of this histogram at 0 highlights that all CPU cores were idle for $\sim 30\%$ of the elapsed time.

FIGURE 5.4: DataSource[0.1.02] Effective CPU Utilization and Concurrency

The second largest column at 1 shows that the application has effectively utilized only a single CPU during the rest of the execution time. This observation is also evident from the thread concurrency histogram. The sharp peak at 1 shows that only one thread was effectively active during $\sim 20\%$ of the elapsed time. The second largest column at 0 indicates another $\sim 7\%$ of the elapsed time when all threads were waiting. Overall, the application performance is almost sequential with both the CPU utilization and concurrency observations far below their theoretical targets.

Figure 5.5 shows the parallel timeline during this test execution. The four timeline tracks represent the time evolution of each thread. The figure also identifies two zones. First 8 seconds of initialization during which the main thread initializes the DataSource. This is followed by the event-loop when all four threads are active. The last time-span of ~ 0.5 seconds shows another single-threaded execution when the results are merged by the main thread. For each thread, the timeline shows the evolution of two states, namely the CPU running and thread spinning activity.

The sources of CPU under-utilization and sub-optimal concurrency are evident from this figure. First, $\sim 28\%$ of the elapsed time is consumed by the serial execution during the initialization. This has a direct impact on both the CPU utilization and thread concurrency. Secondly, during the event-loop execution, there is a frequent spinning activity observed on all threads. This spinning has a non-uniform distribution throughout the event-loop. The most intense spinning is identified by applying a time filter ($16s < T < 22s$) which is shown by the middle inset of the figure. A further filter ($20.5s < T < 21.5s$) is applied to this subset to reveal the zone particularly responsible for this bottleneck. The corresponding inset shows a subset of the call stack during this period along with two metrics, namely CPU Time and CPI Rate. In this case, the CPI Rate is ~ 10 times the ideal, which is a strong indicator of a performance bottleneck. The call stack points to the same mutex lock which was identified as a possible bottleneck during the hot-spot analysis.

Figure 5.6 shows a bottom-up view of the critical call stack relevant to the above-referred mutex. This view uses the metric Wait Time by Thread Concurrency. Referring to this column, $\sim 50\%$ of the wait time is consumed by the call to `ROOT::TReentrantRWLock<std::mutex, ROOT::Internal::RecourseCounts>::WriteLock`. Furthermore, $\sim 30\%$ of the wait time is consumed by its callers. The location of the critical section is identified at one of these caller functions, which is

FIGURE 5.5: DataSource[0.1.02] Parallel Timeline

FIGURE 5.6: DataSource [0.1.02] Critical Call Stack

FIGURE 5.7: DataSource [0.1.02] Critical Section

`TclingClasssInfo::GetBaseOffset`. This function is shown in figure 5.7 along with the metric `Effective Time by Utilization`. This observation indicates the corresponding idle time and poor utilization particularly at the access to the global object `gInterpreterMutex`. At line 609, ROOT acquires the lock for read-write access. The macro `R__LOCKGUARD` defines the scope for this acquisition until the lock guard goes out of scope. Thus, in this case, the lock remains active until the end of the function. This allows only one thread to access the entire function at a time, which impacts the effective concurrency.

5.4.4 Interpretation of Profiling Observations

Both of the hot-spot and concurrency analysis observations indicate poor CPU utilization due to serial execution and excessive spin time. Following conclusions are drawn from these observations:

1. **Explicit Lock:** One of the sources of sub-optimal CPU utilization and concurrency is the explicit read-write lock in the function `TclingClasssInfo::GetBaseOffset`. However, this explicit synchronization is necessary for thread safety due to the global state of `gInterpreter` object. The primary reason for the bottleneck is the serial execution of the entire function. Possible solutions to such bottlenecks include:
 - Eliminate the global state if possible.
 - Reduce the frequency of accessing the global object.
 - Reduce the duration of the lock acquisition.

Following the discussions with `RDataFrame` development team, this bottleneck was independently observed and fixed [41] by Amadio Guilherme and Danilo Piparo of the ROOT development team. The solution was to upgrade `DataSource` to be compliant with ROOT version $\geq 6.14/00$. The section 5.5 reports the results observed from this upgrade.

2. **Initialization Time:** The initialization time for this test case is $\sim 28\%$ of the elapsed time. This is a noticeable serial component affecting the scalability. Apart from noting this as a bottleneck, the objective is also to find other sources affecting the parallelism during the event-loop execution. Referring to this purpose, the CPU utilization and concurrency histograms in figure 5.4 are likely to be biased by the initialization time. In order to observe the influence of initialization time, subsequent plots of relative speedup are generated based on the wall time as well as the event-loop execution time.

5.5 Effect of ROOT's Fix: Version [0.1.03]

This section documents the performance testing of `DataSource[0.1.03]` i.e. The upgrade of `DataSource` to be compliant with ROOT 6.15/01. It reports the performance results and VTune profiles of this version using ROOT 6.15/01 in comparison with `DataSource[0.1.02]` using ROOT 6.13/02.

FIGURE 5.8: DataSource[0.1.02/0.1.03] Wall time split-up

FIGURE 5.9: DataSource[0.1.02/0.1.03] Speedup w.r.t. Sequential Execution

Threads (t)	Speedup [Based on Event-Loop Time]		
	DataSource [0.1.02]	DataSource [0.1.03]	Relative Improvement
	(a)	(b)	$100 * (b - a) / a$
1	0.990	0.991	0.1 %
2	1.698	1.751	3.1 %
3	2.248	2.335	3.9 %
4	2.654	2.813	6.0 %

TABLE 5.3:
DataSource [0.1.02/0.1.03] Comparison of Speedup
Based on Event-Loop

5.5.1 Performance Comparison:

Figure 5.8 shows a comparison of wall, initialization and event-loop execution time for DataSource versions [0.1.02] and [0.1.03]. Figure 5.9 shows comparison of relative speedup with respect to sequential execution. The relevant observations are outlined below:

1. Referring to figure 5.8, both versions show that the initialization time is constant as expected. This observation validates the assumption that the overhead of enabling ImplicitMT feature does not grow with the number of threads. Hence, it can be safely neglected during performance profiling as discussed in section 5.2.1: item 1.
2. Both versions show a similar pattern for the wall time and event-loop execution time. In terms of the wall time, the performance of version [0.1.03] is $\sim 1.6\%$ better in sequential mode, which gradually increases up to $\sim 5.9\%$ for four threads. Similarly, comparing the event-loop execution time, the performance of version [0.1.03] is $\sim 1.5\%$ better in sequential mode, which gradually increases up to $\sim 7\%$ for four threads. For both versions, there is an offset of $\sim 1\%$ between wall time and event-loop execution time. This difference is due to a small improvement in the initialization of ImplicitMT feature of ROOT 6.15/01.
3. Table 5.3 quantifies the improvement of relative speedup based on event-loop execution time. The relative improvement over the last version shows a consistent growth with the increased number of threads. In particular, for ($t = 2$) a growth of 3% indicates the effect of ROOT's fix due to the elimination of a serial component within the event-loop. In addition, this growth doubles in case of ($t = 4$). This observation indicates that the parallelism gained from the fix within the ROOT framework is indeed transparently conveyed to the analysis code.
4. In order to quantify the influence of initialization on these performance plots, the observed speedup based on wall time is compared with that based on event-loop execution time. Table 5.4 lists the difference between these two sets of observations on DataSource [0.1.03]. The relative difference gradually increases with the number of threads in the range [9.0% - 21.6%]. This observation shows that the event-loop fraction indeed scales better. Thus, current observations based on the wall time are still noticeably biased by the initialization. This effect is also observed in the wall time based speedup plot in figure

Threads (t)	Speedup Based on Wall Time (a)	Speedup Based on Event-Loop Time (b)	Relative Difference $100 * (b - a) / a$
1	0.991	0.991	0.0 %
2	1.606	1.751	9.0 %
3	2.015	2.335	15.9 %
4	2.314	2.813	21.6 %

TABLE 5.4: DataSource[0.1.03] Speedup Based on Wall and Event-Loop Time

FIGURE 5.10: DataSource[0.1.03] Effective CPU Utilization and Concurrency

5.9. Specifically, the non-linearity of speedup plot for cases ($t > 2$) causes it to converge towards ~ 2.5 . This motivates to split the scalability study into two separate tasks i.e. with the focus on event-loop and on the initialization. Keeping the initial focus on event-loop, the current test case is revised to maximize the event-loop fraction of elapsed time. Section 5.6 describes a synthetic benchmark used for this purpose.

5.5.2 Profile Difference:

Figure 5.10 shows the histograms of effective CPU utilization and thread concurrency observed with DataSource[0.1.03]. The elapsed time of this particular test execution is 26.2 seconds. Comparing these histograms with the last version (figure 5.4), the relevant observations are outlined below:

1. Referring to the CPU utilization histogram, the Average Effective CPU Utilization is marginally improved from 0.2 to 0.5, which is $\sim 12\%$ of the theoretical Target Utilization. Similar to the last version, the peak of this histogram is persistent at 0. However, the second largest column shows an improvement in the single CPU utilization up to $\sim 38\%$ of the elapsed time. The simultaneous utilization of multiple CPUs is almost zero.
2. Referring to the thread concurrency histogram, the distribution of time for all configurations of simultaneously running threads shows a shift towards the Target Concurrency. However, the peak at 1 still indicates a single threaded execution during $\sim 41\%$ of the elapsed time.
3. Figure 5.11 shows the profile difference between ROOT's version 6.13/02 and 6.15/01 at the location of the last fix. At line 609, the metric `Wait Time Difference`

FIGURE 5.11: DataSource[0.1.02/0.1.03] ROOT's fix: Reduced Critical Section

FIGURE 5.12: DataSource[0.1.02/0.1.03] Effect of lock split-up

by Thread Concurrency shows a total reduction of ~ 7 seconds Wait Time on all threads during the access of read-lock. Comparing this with figure 5.7, the fix refers to the split-up of a single read-write lock into two separate locks. Each of these critical sections now has a smaller period of lock acquisition. This separation allows more threads to simultaneously access parts of the function thereby reducing the probability of lock contention.

4. Figure 5.12 shows one of the critical call stacks along with the difference of Wait Time metric. The concurrency improvement due to the above-referred fix is evident from the elimination of total wait time of ~ 2.4 seconds throughout the entire call stack. Comparing this call stack with figure 5.6, the call chain is indeed originated by the same function `TCLingClassInfo::GetBaseOffset`, which was probed as a bottleneck.

5.6 Synthetic Benchmark

As remarked about the initialization time during the performance comparison in section 5.5.1, it was required to factor out the influence of initialization time on performance results. This is to separate the study of the initialization and the event-loop execution as two independent tasks. This prototype is scoped for the optimization of event-loop, while the initialization is left as an open task for the future work. One solution to collect more profiling samples from within the event-loop is to run the analysis long enough so that the initialization time becomes negligibly small. This section describes a revised test case as a synthetic benchmark to simulate such an expensive analysis. The performance results and profiling observations using this benchmark are discussed. The section concludes with the interpretation of these observations.

5.6.1 Test Setup

The revised test case simulates an expensive operation per event, as described below:

- **Histo1D.Transforms.DataFrame:**
 Reads three `xAOD` vector containers as listed below:
`xAOD::Electrons`, `xAOD::Muons` and `xAOD::Photons`,
 Defines 12 columns, one each for data member of `xAOD::IParticle` interface,
 Applies a transform $f(x) := \sin(x)^2 + \cos(x)^2$, `N` times on each data variable.
 Generates total 36 histograms, 12 for each vector container.

The parameter `N` was iteratively increased and set to 100, such that the analysis runs for at least 6 minutes. The choice of these two parameters is motivated by the objective to keep the initialization time $\leq 2\%$ of the wall time in sequential mode. Table 5.5 documents the execution environment used for this benchmark.

5.6.2 Performance Results

Figure 5.13 shows the wall, initialization and event-loop execution time observed from the above-referred benchmark on `DataSource[0.1.03]`. Referring to the sequential execution, the initialization time is indeed dropped below 1% of the wall time and remains constant with respect to the number of threads. As a consequence,

	DataSource[0.1.03] Test Environment
Hardware	Intel i7 Quad-Core CPU @3.6 GHz, 8GB RAM Hyper-Threading Disabled
OS	Ubuntu 18.04.LTS
ROOT	6.15/01
AnalysisBase	21.2.39
xAODdataSource	0.1.03
Dataset	data17_13TeV.00328263.physics_Main... deriv.DAOD_HIGG2D2.f836_m1824_p3213 Set of 50 compressed DxAOD files Total Size ~25GB

TABLE 5.5: DataSource[0.1.03] Test Environment for Synthetic Benchmark

FIGURE 5.13: DataSource[0.1.03] Wall Time Split-up

FIGURE 5.14: DataSource[0.1.03] Speedup w.r.t sequential execution

Threads (t)	Speedup Based on Wall Time (a)	Speedup Based on Event-Loop Time (b)	Relative Difference $100 * (b - a)/a$
1	1.004	1.004	0.0 %
2	1.808	1.819	0.6 %
3	2.625	2.656	1.2 %
4	3.435	3.496	1.8 %

TABLE 5.6: DataSource[0.1.03] Speedup Based on Wall and Event-Loop Time

the wall and event-loop time now closely follow the same pattern.

Figure 5.14 shows the speedup with respect to the sequential execution. The speedup based on wall time now shows the similar linear pattern as that based on event-loop time. This similarity is quantified by the table 5.6, which compares the speedup values based on wall time and event-loop time. The relative difference between these two sets is well below 2% for all test runs. This observation validates that the influence of initialization time can be now safely ruled out. Thus, the benchmark appears to be suitable for further performance profiling focused on even-loop execution.

5.6.3 Profiling Observations

This section documents the profiling observations on DataSource[0.1.03] with the above-referred benchmark using four threads.

- **Hot-Spot Observations:**

Figure 5.15 shows elapsed time and top hot-spot views. Referring to the elapsed time view, the CPU Time is ~ 3 times that of the elapsed time. This observation is an indicator of improved CPU utilization compared to all previous test runs. In addition, the average CPI rate is fairly close to the ideal target of 0.25. Referring to the top hot-spots view, all top hot-spot functions are from the analysis workload. These functions are illustrated in figure 5.16 sorted by CPU Time. This view also shows total Instructions Retired and corresponding CPI Rate for each function. All call stacks using these top CPU consumers

FIGURE 5.15: DataSource[0.1.03] Elapsed Time and Top Hot-Spots

Source Function / Function / Call Stack	CPU Time [?]	Instructions Retired	CPI Rate
▶ do_cos	63.061s	772,059,600,000	0.294
▶ do_sin	62.292s	454,021,200,000	0.489
▶ __cos_local	52.194s	594,007,200,000	0.318
▶ __sin_local	49.850s	656,726,400,000	0.273
▶ __sincos	27.432s	110,620,800,000	0.883
▶ __copysign	27.400s	327,060,000,000	0.302
▶ operator()	11.439s	39,794,400,000	1.035
▶ libc_feholdsetround_sse_ctx	11.074s	17,539,200,000	2.260
▶ libc_feresetround_sse_ctx	3.066s	21,416,400,000	0.525
▶ std::pow<double, int>	2.935s	30,873,600,000	0.346
▶ [Outside any known module]	2.792s	6,912,000,000	1.341
▶ func@0x9870	1.773s	9,550,800,000	0.658
▶ func@0xbb50	1.015s	4,633,200,000	0.759
▶ __memset_avx2_erms	0.892s	118,800,000	29.030

FIGURE 5.16: DataSource[0.1.03] Hot-Spots sorted by CPU Time

FIGURE 5.17: DataSource[0.1.03] Effective CPU Utilization and Concurrency

are originated from the analysis transform function $f(x) := \sin(x)^2 + \cos(x)^2$. There are two functions with high CPI Rate affecting a larger instruction set, namely `operator()` and `libc_feholdsetround_sse_ctx`. However, none of these represent overhead caused by ROOT framework or the DataSource implementation.

- **Concurrency Observations:**

Figure 5.17 shows the histograms of effective CPU utilization and thread concurrency. In comparison with the last observed results in figure 5.10, the relevant observations are outlined below:

1. The Average Effective CPU Utilization is slightly improved from 0.5 to 0.8, which is $\sim 20\%$ of the theoretical Target Utilization. Compared to the observations from the last test case (figure 5.10) the peak of this histogram is now shifted from 0 to 1. In addition, the utilization of single CPU is now spanned over $\sim 85\%$ of the elapsed time. However, there is no change in the simultaneous utilization of multiple CPUs. This observation is as expected because the only change in this test case is the increased workload during event-loop execution.
2. Referring to the thread concurrency, the peak of this histogram at 4 shows that all threads were simultaneously running for $\sim 70\%$ of the elapsed time. However, $\sim 18\%$ of the elapsed time refers to two simultaneously running threads. This observation hints about the existence of possible synchronization overheads.
3. Figure 5.18 shows the parallel timeline with four metrics, namely Thread Running, Thread Waits, CPU Time, and Spin/Overhead Time evolved over the elapsed time. The event-loop begins at ($T = 7s$) when all four threads are initialized. At ($T = 95s$), the CPU Time and CPU Running metrics show that two of the threads are finishing their tasks much before the others. This workload imbalance is further revealed by applying a time filter ($94s < T < 111s$). The inset within the figure shows a call stack of the most waiting object within this filtered time-span. The root of this tree points to a `Futex` synchronization lock used by the TBB thread scheduler. This lock serves the purpose of joining the background threads to the main thread before the application exits. The `Wait Time` metric shows $\sim 33s$ of thread time lost due to idling threads. The small `Wait Count`

FIGURE 5.18: DataSource[0.1.02] Parallel Timeline: Workload Imbalance

FIGURE 5.19: DataSource[0.1.02] Parallel Timeline: Synchronization Overhead

refers to the three worker threads, each one waiting only once after completion of its task. The `Spin Time` metric indicates no noticeable spinning overhead during this filtered time-span.

4. Figure 5.19 shows the same parallel timeline with the above-referred metrics. At ($T = 7s$) i.e. just after the beginning of event-loop, the `CPU Time` is reduced on three background threads compared to that of the main thread. Also, `Thread Running` and `Thread Waits` metrics indicate that all three background threads are waiting up to ($T = 14s$).

The above-referred imbalance of thread concurrency is further revealed by applying a time filter ($6s < T < 14s$). The inset within this figure shows a call stack of the top waiting object, which is a synchronization lock. The `Wait Time by Thread Concurrency` metric indicates ~ 6 seconds lost during this filtered time-span. Referring to the first row, a high value of `total Wait Count` and a relatively small value of `total Spin Time` hints about a synchronization overhead with fine granularity. The lock is probably being acquired for a small period but at a higher frequency. The leaf of the call stack tree points to the source of this synchronization overhead due to a read-write lock used in the function `TBufferFile::ReadClassBuffer`.

5.6.4 Interpretation of Profiling Observations

The hot-spot observations show that the `DataSource` implementation is performing transparently during the event-loop without adding any noticeable abstraction overheads. However, referring to the CPU utilization and concurrency histograms, there is a scope for scalability improvement. The concurrency observations indicate two sources of the performance bottleneck. The most significant is the imbalanced workload distribution by `DataSource`. The second one is a relatively small synchronization overhead within the `ROOT` framework. The rest of this chapter documents an optimization attempt to address the workload imbalance. This is followed by the performance and profiling observations on the revised version of `DataSource`.

5.7 Optimization of Workload: Version [0.3.00]

This section describes the implementation and testing of `DataSource[0.3.00]`, i.e. the upgrade for optimum workload distribution. It begins with a problem statement and describes the optimization concept, followed by its implementation details. The section concludes with the comparison of the performance and profiling observations with the last version.

5.7.1 Optimization Concept:

As described in section 4.8.2, the `DataSource` splits the entire event range into sub-ranges during initialization. The `DataFrame` interprets these ranges as independent tasks and allocates them to worker threads on their corresponding slots. The initial implementation – `DataSource[0.1.03]` uses a uniform distribution strategy for this split-up. As discussed in section 4.9.1, this split-up ensures that each thread gets an equal number of events and exactly one task. In particular, the condition ($nTasks == nSlots$) always holds. This implementation has two consequences as outlined below:

1. **Reduced Parallelism:** As described in section 3.3.3, the `DataFrame` relies on Intel TBB framework for task scheduling and thread-pool management. The task-based parallelism allows threads to pick up next available task after completion of the current task. Therefore, a workload with finer granularity provides better opportunities to use the available parallelism. The condition ($nTasks == nSlots$) referred above, defeats this purpose due to a coarse granularity. Therefore, one of the optimization objectives is to minimize the task size.

On the other hand, “too small” task size tends to incur overheads due to frequently interrupted I/O activity. Therefore, a low frequency of sufficiently long and contiguous read-write operations usually help to improve the I/O throughput. Consequently, the task size is a tread-off between the granularity and the I/O performance. This tread-off refines the problem statement to minimize the task size and maximize the span of contiguous I/O activity.

2. **Loss of Generality:** Using the event count for task size makes the workload distribution dependent on the type of analysis and input data. In general, the analysis may have complex event filters to skip some sub-sets of events. The outcome of such filtered subsets cannot be assumed to have equal distribution on all slots. Similarly, based on specific conditions used by analysis, the distribution and sparsity of data may affect the workload distribution over the event range. Some tasks may process more expensive operations than others. The `DataSource` cannot have prior information about such parameters affecting the load distribution. Therefore, the “event count” does not suit well as a unit of task size. As the I/O performance is one of the influencing factors, choosing the smallest compression unit is a suitable alternative to the event count.

As described in section 3.2.4, `ROOT` follows a three-step sequence for reading the data from a disk. This includes reading compressed buffers from a file, followed by their de-compression and de-serialization. The basket clustering feature allows `ROOT` to read multiple baskets as a single cluster. Thus, the cluster represents a large chunk of data read by a single contiguous I/O operation. The outcome of such a single read is a set of multiple compressed basket buffers, ready to be de-compressed and de-serialized by multiple threads concurrently [21]. Following the discussions with the `ROOT:RDataFrame` development team, a solution was devised to set the task size dynamically at runtime such that each task will process one cluster of baskets. This choice fulfills all requirements as outlined below:

1. **Improved Parallelism:** Processing one cluster per task reduces the task size. This reduction ensures the required condition ($nTasks \gg nSlots$) thereby providing better opportunities for TBB task scheduler to utilize the available parallelism.
2. **Optimum I/O Throughput:** Any task processing smaller number events than that contained in a cluster, would cause redundant de-compression of baskets. On the other hand, processing multiple clusters per task would coarsen the granularity of workload. Hence, aligning the tasks to cluster boundaries would be an appropriate choice for optimum I/O throughput.
3. **Generality:** The workload distribution is no more dependent on the event count. The use of cluster size decouples it from the complexity of analysis and the sparsity of data.

FIGURE 5.20: DataSource[0.1.03/0.3.00] Wall time split-up

5.7.2 Implementation

Based on the feedback and suggestions given by Enrico Guiraud and Danilo Piparo from the ROOT development team, it was observed that a similar implementation of this concept is already being used by ROOT: `TTreeProcessorMT` [60] class. The DataSource adapts its implementation for the current version. This execution sequence is described below:

During the initialization, the DataSource creates a transient instance of TChain [52] class using the input data set. It then iterates over all data files using TChainElement [53] class, which represents an instance of a data file. For each file, the DataSource iterates over all available basket clusters using TClusterIterator [54] class. This iterator provides the event numbers corresponding to the start and end of each cluster. The DataSource uses this information for populating a collection of tasks. The DataFrame then collects these tasks and schedules them on slots for concurrent execution.

5.7.3 Performance Comparison:

The implementation described above was retested using the same benchmark Histo1D.Transforms. Figure 5.20 compares the performance plots between two implementations, i.e. DataSource[0.1.03] with uniform task distribution and DataSource[0.3.00] with tasks aligned to clusters. For both versions, the wall and event-loop time are in close agreement. This observation validates that the new workload distribution strategy has not affected the influence of initialization time on the wall time. Furthermore, the initialization time is still constant with respect to the number of threads and well below 1% of the sequential wall time as expected.

FIGURE 5.21: DataSource [0.1.03/0.3.00] Speedup w.r.t sequential execution

Threads (t)	Speedup [Based on Event-Loop Time]		
	DataSource [0.1.03] (a)	DataSource [0.3.00] (b)	Relative Improvement $100 * (b - a) / a$
1	1.004	0.996	-0.8 %
2	1.819	1.995	9.7 %
3	2.656	2.973	11.9 %
4	3.496	3.924	12.2 %

TABLE 5.7: DataSource [0.1.03/0.3.00] Speedup Comparison

FIGURE 5.22: DataSource[0.3.00] Effective CPU Utilization and Concurrency

Figure 5.21 compares the relative speedup between these two versions. The scalability improvement due to cluster based distribution is evident from the increased speedup for ($t > 1$) on DataSource[0.3.00] plots. Table 5.7 quantifies this improvement showing a consistent growth up to $\sim 12\%$. However, a particular observation for ($t = 1$) indicates 0.8% performance penalty. This overhead is anticipated due to the sequential loop introduced for reading cluster information during the initialization.

5.7.4 Profile Difference:

Figure 5.22 shows histograms of CPU utilization and thread concurrency observations from the profiling of DataSource[0.3.00] using four threads. The total elapsed time of this test run was 103 seconds. In comparison with the last version (figure 5.17) the relevant observations are outlined below:

1. The Average Effective CPU Utilization is improved from 0.8 to 3.6, which is 90% of the theoretical Target Utilization. The peak of this histogram at 4 shows that all CPUs were simultaneously utilized for $\sim 87\%$ of the elapsed time. The second largest column at 1 indicates the usage of single CPU for $\sim 7\%$ of the elapsed time. This duration is attributed to the initialization of DataSource.
2. Referring to the thread concurrency, the peak of this histogram shows all threads simultaneously running for $\sim 68\%$ of the elapsed time. The second largest column at 1, reproduces the same observation as CPU utilization i.e. a single threaded execution for $\sim 7\%$ of the elapsed time. Remaining three columns of this histogram i.e. at 0, 2, and 3 indicate a possible thread contention costing $\sim 5\%$ of the elapsed time.
3. Figure 5.23 shows the profile difference between DataSource[0.1.03] and DataSource[0.3.00] sorted by the Wait Time metric. This figure lists three top waiting objects with the first one expanded to show its call stack. A 30.5 seconds difference of Wait Time within the first call stack validates the performance gained by the TBB scheduler due to the alignment of tasks to clusters. In terms of Wall Time, this reduction reflects in the last ~ 15 seconds of the event-loop as observed in the timeline of figure 5.24 compared to the last version (figure 5.18). By visual inspection, the timeline of figure 5.24 shows a

FIGURE 5.23: DataSource [0.1.03/0.3.00] Profile Difference sorted by Wait Time

FIGURE 5.24: DataSource [0.3.00] Parallel Timeline

better workload distribution across all threads compared to the last version. The interpretation of this observation is discussed in the following section.

4. Referring to figure 5.23, the last two rows indicate a performance bottleneck persistent in both versions. This observation is attributed to the sub-optimal concurrency during to the period ($6s < T < 14s$) as observed in figures 5.19 and 5.24. The source of this bottleneck is discussed in section 5.8.

5.7.5 Interpretation of Optimization Results

1. Comparison of wall time and profiling observations with respect to the last version validates that the performance gain is indeed due to the reduction of wait time corresponding to the workload imbalance. Furthermore, it also validates that the new workload distribution strategy did not introduce any more bottlenecks within the event-loop.

Thread Rank (r)	Thread-Local Elapsed Time (a)	Normalized Elapsed Time (b) = a/a[1]
1	107.791	1.000
2	104.500	0.969
3	89.000	0.826
4	88.000	0.816
Mean $\pm \sigma$	97.323 \pm10.284	0.903 \pm0.095

TABLE 5.8: DataSource[0.1.03] Thread-Local Elapsed Time

Thread Rank (r)	Thread-Local Elapsed Time (a)	Normalized Elapsed Time (b) = a/a[1]
1	96.500	1.000
2	94.340	0.978
3	94.320	0.977
4	94.240	0.977
Mean $\pm \sigma$	94.850 \pm1.101	0.983 \pm0.011

TABLE 5.9: DataSource[0.3.00] Thread-Local Elapsed Time

2. The complexity of thread executions and difference of wall time values makes it difficult to define a general metric to measure the improvement in the workload distribution. However, an attempt is made to quantify it with reference to an ideal scenario in which all threads get an equal workload and finish their execution simultaneously. To this end, the thread-local elapsed time is used as an indicator metric. In order to eliminate the effect of different versions on elapsed times, this metric is normalized by using its maximum value. For a given thread, the normalized elapsed time refers to a weight of its workload with respect to the maximum workload. To keep the focus on event-loop execution, the initialization time is subtracted from the elapsed time of main threads. Furthermore, as the sequence of thread execution is unimportant, the observed values are sorted by thread-local elapsed time and are identified by

FIGURE 5.25: DataSource[0.1.03/0.3.00] Thread-Local Normalized Elapsed Time

their sorted index referred to as the rank. Thus, rank 1 refers to a thread execution corresponding to the maximum workload.

Tables 5.8 shows the thread-local data collected from profiling results of DataSource[0.1.03]. Similarly, table 5.9 shows the same metrics collected from the profiling results of DataSource[0.3.00]. Figure 5.25 shows corresponding plots of normalized elapsed time with respect to thread ranks. From a comparison of normalized elapsed time columns in both tables, DataSource[0.3.00] shows ~ 8.6 times smaller standard deviation, which is a good indicator of workload improvement. This observation is also evident from the linearity and near-zero slope of its graph for ($r > 1$) in figure 5.25. Referring to the case of ($r = 1$) a difference of 0.02 compared to rest of the ranks is attributed to a workload imbalance contributed by two components as below:

- A synchronization overhead at the beginning of event-loop as discussed in section 5.7.4 item 4.
 - An additional workload on the main thread for merging the thread-local results at the end of event-loop.
3. From the wall time observations, the special case of ($t = 1$) shows that this optimization attempt has introduced a constant cost during the initialization. This overhead is due to the sequential loop used for reading the cluster information from a file. Thus, it has a potential for improvement using parallelism. This effort is left as an open task for future work.

Source Function / Function / Call Stack	CPU Time ▾	CPI Rate	Wait Rate	Instructions Retired
▶ do_cos	68.204s	0.381	0.000	632,852,679,095
▶ do_sin	67.694s	0.382	0.000	630,333,316,539
▶ __cos_local	56.378s	0.381	0.000	523,749,672,057
▶ __sin_local	51.653s	0.381	0.000	482,183,859,722
▶ __sincos	29.781s	0.383	0.000	276,007,604,834
▶ __copysign	28.543s	0.381	0.000	266,396,678,281
▶ operator()	12.460s	0.381	0.000	115,804,339,162
▶ libc_feholdsetround_sse_ctx	11.925s	0.380	0.000	111,359,285,305
▶ libc_feresetround_sse_ctx	3.381s	0.380	0.000	31,829,069,788
▶ std::pow<double, int>	3.140s	0.381	0.000	29,198,183,383
▶ func@0x9870	2.313s	0.553	0.000	14,757,720,917
▶ [vmlinux]	1.700s	0.255	0.361	92,058,252,022
▶ [ld.so.cache]	1.397s	0.384	0.000	12,856,381,154
▶ func@0xbb50	1.106s	0.378	0.000	10,474,040,525
▶ __memset_avx2_erms	1.079s	0.387	0.000	9,951,978,763
▶ TExMap::GetValue	0.822s	0.673	0.000	4,095,875,051
▶ __memmove_avx_unaligned_erms	0.771s	0.451	0.000	6,081,570,272
▶ do_sincos_1	0.728s	0.380	0.000	6,625,987,273
▶ std::_fill_a<void**, void*>	0.676s	0.384	0.000	6,286,965,136

FIGURE 5.26: DataSource[0.3.00] Hot-Spots sorted by CPU Time

5.8 Performance Analysis: Version[0.3.00]

This section documents further profiling analysis of DataSource[0.3.00] using the same benchmark test with four threads. The previous section was mainly focused on performance difference compared to the last version. This section takes a closer look at synchronization overheads in the latest version. It documents the hot-spot and concurrency analysis and concludes with remarks about known limitations.

5.8.1 Profiling Observations

Figure 5.26 shows top hot-spot functions sorted by the CPU Time metric. The list of hot-spots does not indicate any expensive CPU user from ROOT or DataSource. Referring to the CPU Time and Instructions Retired columns, most of the CPU time is used by the top eight hot-spots. For all these hot-spots, the CPI Rate shows all values consistently close to the ideal CPI of 0.25. Referring to the Wait Rate column, there is a non-zero value corresponding to a system call [vmlinux]. This observation hints about a possible bottleneck. Although for this test case it affects a relatively smaller fraction of CPU Time.

Figure 5.27 shows the parallel timeline observed with the concurrency analysis. This view shows a time evolution of Thread Running, Context Switches, and Spin Time metrics. At time ($T = 4s$) the event-loop begins with the initialization of all three background threads. Immediately after this point there is a small period affected by spinning. This period is expanded in the inset, which shows corresponding spin time distribution during the period [$4.0s < T < 5.3s$]. The main thread appears to execute continuously, whereas all the background threads show frequent spinning activity.

Figure 5.28 shows the call stack of [vmlinux] with all metrics filtered by the above-referred period. Referring to the CPI Rate column, the highest value points to a read-write mutex lock located in the function TBufferFile::ReadClassBuffer. This

FIGURE 5.27: DataSource[0.3.00] Parallel Timeline

Filtered by time span [4.0s < t < 5.3s]

Source Function / Function / Call Stack	CPU Time ▾	CPI Rate	Wait Rate	Instructions Retired
▼ [vmlinux]	0.644s	1.043	0.093	2,911,777,203
▼ [vmlinux]	0.644s	1.043	0.093	2,911,777,203
▼ [vmlinux]	0.632s	1.045	0.093	2,877,362,810
▼ [vmlinux]	0.631s	1.045	0.093	2,875,411,606
▼ [vmlinux]	0.630s	1.044	0.093	2,872,466,114
▼ [vmlinux]	0.626s	1.046	0.093	2,865,565,177
▼ [vmlinux]	0.625s	1.079	0.093	2,697,920,543
▼ [vmlinux]	0.618s	1.074	0.093	2,689,486,607
▼ futex_wake	0.343s	1.557	0.000	562,703,101
▼ __pthread_cond_broadcast	0.343s	1.557	0.000	562,703,101
▼ std::condition_variable::notify_all	0.343s	1.557	0.000	562,703,101
▼ __gthread_mutex_unlock	0.186s	1.622	0.000	276,682,422
▼ std::mutex::unlock	0.186s	1.622	0.000	276,682,422
▼ std::lock_guard<std::mutex>::~lock_guard	0.186s	1.622	0.000	276,682,422
▼ std::_V2::condition_variable_any::notify_all	0.186s	1.622	0.000	276,682,422
▼ ROOT::TReentrantRWLock<std::mutex, RC	0.186s	1.622	0.000	276,682,422
▼ ROOT::TVirtualRWMutex::UnLock	0.177s	1.678	0.000	250,025,716
▼ TLockGuard::~TLockGuard	0.177s	1.678	0.000	250,025,716
▼ TBufferFile::ReadClassBuffer	0.177s	1.678	0.000	250,025,716
▼ TBranch::Streamer	0.094s	1.560	0.000	132,454,237
▶ TStreamerBase::ReadBuffer	0.094s	1.560	0.000	132,454,237

Critical Section →

FIGURE 5.28: DataSource[0.3.00] Critical Call Stack

observation identifies a source of synchronization overhead within the ROOT framework. However, a detailed study of this bottleneck is considered beyond the scope of this prototype.

5.8.2 Known limitations

Referring to the interpretations of optimization results discussed in section 5.7.5 and further profiling observations in this section, two known performance bottlenecks are outlined as below:

1. The initialization phase contributes a noticeable serial component ($\sim 7\%$ of the wall time). This needs to be investigated for possible use of parallelism.
2. The read-write mutex lock in the function `TBufferFile::ReadClassBuffer` affects a section of event-loop and has a potential for improvement. On the synthetic benchmark, its impact is observed to be relatively small. However, some more complex use cases may be used to investigate its effect on real analyses.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The objective of this thesis is to prototype a proof-of-concept implementation of the ATLAS xAOD data source and investigate its potential to integrate ROOT's `RDataFrame` interface with the ATLAS analysis framework. As described in chapter 4, this work aimed to establish a link between the ATLAS event store and `RDataFrame`. Concretely, the deliverable of this prototype – the `xAODdataSource` package introduced a framework layer between ATLAS EDM and `RDataFrame`. The integration tests (section: 4.10.2) and performance results (section: 5.7.5) demonstrate that the first implementation of this prototype is functional and scalable, thus validates the proof-of-concept.

Apart from the stability and correctness, the prime goal referred above – *the potential to be used within ATLAS analysis framework* has steered its design objectives (section: 4.3). The `DataSource` accomplishes these objectives using the building blocks of ATLAS EDM features (chapter: 2) and `ROOT::RDataFrame` interface (chapter: 3).

Referring to the scalability and minimal abstraction overhead, this prototype is evolved through three versions. Figure 6.1 shows a summary of important speedup observations made during this process. The findings and conclusions from the results of these three versions are summarized below:

1. Preliminary Results [0.1.02] :

The preliminary results discussed in section 5.2 showed poor scalability on all the test cases with speedup saturating beyond two threads. Following conclusions are drawn from these results:

- The observations made from preliminary results showed that the scalability of `DataSource[0.1.02]` implementation is independent of the hardware, provided that the disk latency is factored out. The subsequent performance testing and profiling were thus carried out on the same hardware configuration namely, SSD with warm cache mode. This necessitates a re-validation of the latest version with alternative hardware environments. However, this is considered as a task for future work.
- Referring to figure 6.1, a representative test case `Histo1D.SingleVariable.0102` summarizes the observations from preliminary results. This plot sets a baseline reference for the scalability of later versions. However, these results represent the analyses involving a relatively small workload and fewer I/O operations. Using a larger data set `Histo1D.MultipleContainers` showed that the initialization of `DataSource` was affecting the speedup observations of short running analyses. Referring to figure 6.1, the improvement observed with this dataset `Histo1D`.

FIGURE 6.1: Summary of Speedup with respect to Sequential Execution

MultipleContainers.0102 compared to that with Histo1D.SingleVariable.0102 is interpreted as a consequence of increased execution time. In this case, the serial component of initialization diminishes with longer running analyses.

2. Identification of Bottleneck [0.1.03] :

The performance analysis followed in section 5.4 revealed a synchronization bottleneck due to a mutex lock. This limitation was resolved after the upgrade of DataSource to use ROOT version $\geq 6.15/00$, which had the corresponding fix.

- The observations made after this upgrade Histo1D.MultipleContainers.0103 show up to $\sim 6\%$ improvement in the speedup based on event-loop time. Table 5.3, shows growth in relative improvement with the increased number of threads. In addition, figure 5.10 shows concurrency improvement with 2, 3 and 4 threads simultaneously running for a longer duration. These observations show that the parallelism gained from ROOT's fix is transparently conveyed to the user analysis.
- The table 5.4 shows up to a $\sim 21\%$ relative difference between the speedup based on wall time and that based on event-loop time. In order to focus on event-loop, this effect was eliminated by using a synthetic benchmark (section 5.6). The effectiveness of this benchmark is evident from the relative difference of less than 2% as shown in table 5.6. Referring to figure 6.1, the linearity of plot Histo1D.Transforms.0103 compared to that of Histo1D.MultipleContainers.0103 shows the influence of initialization time on short running analyses. This observation indicates the requirement of additional optimization efforts specifically focused on the initialization of DataSource.

3. Performance Optimization [0.3.00] :

The optimization strategy (section 5.7.1) used for `DataSource` [0.3.00] has improved the workload distribution without adding any abstraction overheads within the event-loop. Referring to figure 6.1, the effectiveness of this update is evident from the linear plot of `Histo1D.Transforms.0300` with a slope fairly close to that of the ideal speedup. Following conclusions are drawn from the observations of the current version of `DataSource`.

- Referring to the table 5.7, the relative improvement consistently grows with the number of threads up to $\sim 12\%$. In addition, the comparison of tables 5.8 and 5.9 shows ~ 8.6 times reduction in the standard deviation of normalized thread-local elapsed time.
- A particular observation from the first row of table 5.7 shows that the parallel implementation is currently causing a small performance penalty on single threaded execution. However, this is interpreted as an exceptional use case, which will not occur in the user analysis workflow. This is because the `ImplicitMT` feature is expected to be disabled during the sequential execution. Nevertheless, this overhead can be later eliminated during the optimization of initialization.
- The profiling results described in section 5.8 validate that the current version of the `DataSource` does not introduce any noticeable abstraction overheads to the event-loop implementation. However, it has two known limitations as outlined below:
 - (a) The effect of initialization on the performance of short running analyses needs a closer look for optimization. The constant cost of initialization would be especially noticeable when running interactive analysis jobs within a ROOT session.
 - (b) The synchronization overhead due to the mutex lock in the function `TBufferFile::ReadClassBuffer`, appears to be marginal. However, a detailed study of its impact on complex use cases is left as an open task for future work.

Based on the current findings the following updates are suggested for further improvements:

- The initialization sequence of `DataSource` can be optimized by using parallelism. There are two functional units of code potentially suitable for parallelism during initialization. 1. The initialization of meta-data from the ATLAS event store. 2. The decomposition of workload into tasks.
- The current implementation supports read-only data access. This can be further extended to other access methods described in section 2.6. In particular, additional implementations of `IHandle` interface are possible, which can support read-write data handles or tool handles. This extension will allow the `DataSource` to support more complex use cases.
- The performance testing and profiling of this prototype were done using a stand-alone desktop environment. This effort needs to be complemented by testing this implementation on alternative hardware. Such a study would provide insights into the suitability of the current solution for a wider range of execution environments.

Appendix A

Unit Tests

All unit tests currently used by `DataSource` are documented below. For each test, the pre-conditions and post-conditions are documented along with relevant assumptions for each unit under test.

1. `MakeDataFrameTest.ThrowOnEmptyFilePattern`: This test validates that the factory function `make_xAODdataFrame` throws a run-time exception, if the input file name pattern is empty.
2. `MakeDataFrameTest.ThrowOnInvalidFileName`: This test validates that the factory function `make_xAODdataFrame` throws a run-time exception, if the input file name pattern does not yield any valid data files. This may happen due to incorrect specification of file name pattern or missing input files at the specified path.
3. `MakeDataFrameTest.ThrowOnEmptyTreeName`: By default, the `DataSource` assumes the xAOD tree name as `CollectionTree`. However it allows analyst to provide custom tree name to support user defined xAOD files. This test validates that the factory function `make_xAODdataFrame` throws a run-time exception if the tree name is not correctly initialized due to errors in analysis configuration.
4. `MakeDataFrameTest.MakeDataFrameWithValidFileNamePattern`: This test validates that the factory function `make_xAODdataFrame` successfully creates and initializes an instance of `RDataFrame` provided the correct file name pattern is specified; and all data files are accessible.
5. `MakeDataFrameTest.ValidateSizePerInputFile`: This test uses a small data set to create an instance of `RDataFrame`. It validates that the newly created data frame holds the correct number of events exactly equal to those available in the input data set.
6. `SetNSlotsTest.ThrowOnZeroSlots` This test validates that the function `SetNSlots` throws a run-time exception if `RDataFrame` fails to initialize number of slots.
7. `SetNSlotsTest.SetOneSlots`: This test validates that the `DataSource` correctly initializes itself when `RDataFrame` uses one slot for execution.
8. `SetNSlotsTest.SetMultipleSlots`: This test validates that the `DataSource` correctly initializes itself when `RDataFrame` uses all available slots for execution.
9. `HasColumnTest.ReturnFalseOnMissingColumn`: This test validates that the function `HasColumn` returns false, if the column name requested by `RDataFrame` does not exist in the input data set.

10. `HasColumnTest.ReturnTrueOnExistingColumn`: This test validates that the function `HasColumn` returns true, if the column name requested by `RDataFrame` does not exist in the input data set.
11. `GetColumnNamesTest.MultipleColumnNames`: This test validates that the function `GetColumnNames` returns a vector of correct size and column names exactly matching the available columns of input data set.
12. `GetTypeNamesTest.ThrowOnMissingColumn`: This test validates that the function `GetTypeNames` throws a run-time exception if the column name requested by `RDataFrame` does not exist in the input data set.
13. `GetTypeNamesTest.ReturnTypeNameOnValidColumnName`: This test validates that the function `GetTypeNames` correctly returns the expected type name for a valid column requested by `RDataFrame`.
14. `GetColumnReadersTest.ThrowOnMissingColumn`: This test validates that the function `GetColumnReaders` throws a run-time exception if the column name requested by `RDataFrame` does not exist in the input data set.
15. `GetColumnReadersTest.ThrowOnMismatchedType`: This test validates that the function `GetColumnReaders` throws a run-time exception if the column name requested by `RDataFrame` does not correctly match with the expected type in the input data set. This may happen due to an error in analysis code, such that another column with the name requested by the analyst exists, but the data type of that variable does not match with that expected by `RDataFrame`.
16. `GetEntryRangesTest.ReturnMultipleRangesForMultipleClusters` This test validates that the function `GetEntryRanges` creates a correct number of tasks exactly matching the number of clusters available in the input data set.

Appendix B

RDataFrame Features

Following tables document currently supported features of RDataFrame interface.

Transformation	Description
Define	Creates a new column in the dataset based on user-defined function for transformation.
DefineSlot	Same and Define, the user-defined function gets the slot number. Allows the user to write thread-safe transformation.
DefineSlotEntry	Same and DefineSlot, user-defined function gets entry number in addition to slot number. Allows the user-defined function to use entry number as a parameter for transformation.
Filter	Defines a selection criterion for execution of event based on user-defined function.
Range	Creates a node in the function call graph that filters events based on specified range.

TABLE B.1: RDataFrame Transformations

Lazy Action	Description
Aggregate	Executes a user-defined accumulation operation on the processed column values.
Book	Books execution of a custom action using a user-defined helper object.
DefineSlotEntry	Same and DefineSlot, user-defined function gets entry number in addition to slot number. Allows the user-defined function to use entry number as a parameter for transformation.
Cache	Caches in contiguous memory columns' entries. Custom columns can be cached as well, filtered entries are not cached. Users can specify which columns to save (default is all).
Count	Returns the number of events processed.
Display	Obtains the events in the dataset for the requested columns. The method returns an RDisplay instance which can be queried to get a compressed tabular representation on the standard output or a complete representation as a string.

Fill	Fill a user defined object with the values of the specified branches, as if by calling “Obj.Fill(branch1, branch2, ...)”.
Graph	Fills a TGraph with the two columns provided. If Multi-threading is enabled, the order of the points may not be the one expected, it is therefore suggested to sort it before drawing.
Histo {1D,2D,3D}	Fill a {one, two, three} dimensional histogram with the processed branch values.
Max	Return the maximum of processed branch values. If the type of the column is inferred, the return type is double, the type of the column otherwise.
Mean	Return the mean of processed branch values.
Min	Return the minimum of processed branch values. If the type of the column is inferred, the return type is double, the type of the column otherwise.
Profile {1D,2D}	Fill a {one, two} dimensional profile with the branch values that passed all filters.
Reduce	Reduce (e.g., sum, merge) entries using the function (lambda, functor...) passed as an argument. The function must have signature T(T, T) where T is the type of the branch. Return the final result of the reduction operation. An optional parameter allows initialization of the result object to non-default values.
Report	Obtains statistics on how many entries have been accepted and rejected by the filters. See the section on named filters for a more detailed explanation. The method returns a RCutFlowReport instance which can be queried programmatically to get information about the effects of the individual cuts
StdDev	Returns the unbiased standard deviation of the processed branch values.
Sum	Returns the sum of the values in the column. If the type of the column is inferred, the return type is double, the type of the column otherwise.
Take	Extracts a column from the dataset as a collection of values. If the type of the column is a C-style array, the type stored in the return container is a ROOT::VecOps::RVec<T> to guarantee the lifetime of the data involved.

TABLE B.2: RDataFrame Lazy Actions

Instant Actions	Description
Foreach	Executes a user-defined function on each entry. Users are responsible for the thread-safety of this lambda when executing with implicit multi-threading enabled.
ForeachSlot	Same as Foreach, but the user-defined function must take an extra unsigned int slot as its first parameter. Each slot will take a different value, 0 to nThreads - 1, for each thread of execution. This is meant to be a helper in writing thread-safe Foreach actions when using RDataFrame after ROOT::EnableImplicitMT(). ForeachSlot works just as well with single-thread execution: in that case, the slot will always be 0.
Snapshot	Writes processed dataset to disk, in a new TTree and TFile. Custom columns can be saved as well. Filtered entries are not saved. Users can specify which columns to save (default is all). Snapshot, by default, overwrites the output file if it already exists. The snapshot can be made lazy by setting the appropriate flag in the snapshot options.

TABLE B.3: RDataFrame Instant Actions

Operation	Description
Aliase	Introduces an alias for a particular column name.
GetColumnNames	Gets the names of all the available columns of the dataset.
GetDefinedColumnNames	Gets the names of all the defined columns
GetColumnType	Returns the type of a given column as a string.
GetColumnTypeNamesList	Returns the list of type names of columns in the dataset.
GetFilterNames	Gets all the filters defined. If called on a root node, all filters will be returned. For any other node, only the filters upstream of that node.
Display	Provides an ASCII representation of the columns types and contents of the dataset printable by the user.
SaveGraph	Stores the computation graph of RDataFrame in graphviz format for easy inspection.

TABLE B.4: RDataFrame Other Operations

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